

3.1

Platform v1

including

documentation

tool

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes the process of designing and creating **the Made4You platform**, a repository of co-created health care solutions improving the quality of life of people with physical limitations. The platform includes also digital **documentation tool** both enabling collaborative and decentralized development of solutions and supporting their replicability.

The main target groups of the platform are:

- care recipients (people with physical limitations) and their carers (CR);
- healthcare professionals (HP);
- designers, engineers, makers (DEM).

Due to this heterogeneity of users the process requires a co-design approach so that the platform can be a real helpful and easy-to-use tool. Therefore, different techniques have been experimented, from shadowing to survey, with the goals of collecting feedback, understanding users' behaviors towards health-related issues and, more generally, fostering active engagement.

This document details all the activities carried out that led to both Platform v1 and Documentation Template v1. It is addressed to Made4You consortium as well as interested individuals or organizations. Consequently, it is conceived with a double function: on one hand it shares widely the research and their results (analysis) and, on the other hand, it acts as an operating and simple document that sets choices and conclusions for future platform developments (synthesis).

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List of abbreviations

CR	Care recipient
DEM	Designers, engineers, makers
HP	Healthcare professional
PU	Platform User
TOG	Together to Go Foundation
WP	Workpackage
ZSI	Centre for Social Innovation – ZSI

1. Introduction

Social and collaborative innovation in healthcare sector is taking place. On one hand, people are increasingly self-managing their own needs and a growing movement around people-centered approaches to healthcare is generating bottom-up solutions. On the other hand, disciplines like *Design for Care* have established themselves as concrete opportunities for designers, makers, engineers to do something meaningful for someone else.

Nevertheless, there are still some missing enablers for this innovation:

- an online infrastructure aimed to collect, organize, help document, and share existing health&care solutions for people facing physical limitations;
- a collection of solutions driven by use of digital fabrication techniques - not simply frugal ideas or proof of concepts - that can be made anywhere;
- effective documentation of “recipes” explaining how to make the solutions.

Within this framework, the Made4You project is targeting people with disabilities and healthcare professionals with health&care products made by means of digital fabrication technologies. To make the solutions available, the Made4You project provides a platform where people can search for what they need to foster their autonomy. Each solution is documented, that means that it is fully described by its functionality, assembly guides, bill of materials and design files.

Furthermore, the Made4You platform is not designed from scratch but is co-designed, and collaboratively created with the involvement of 4 categories of stakeholder groups:

- people in search for a solution (a person with a healthcare need, carer or healthcare professional), or who can provide feedback on a specific solution;
- engineers, software developers, makers and designers responsible for the documentation, blueprints and technical specifications;
- donors, co-funders and crowdfunders;
- Information Technology law specialists, Intellectual Property specialists and ethicists able to define and implement the necessary legislation, liability and data protection within the documentation tool and the platform.

To such purpose the participatory design process uses different design tools, iterative co-development by all stakeholder groups, with the support of technical experts, and chronological and successive versions of documentation templates

and platforms up to the final deliverable: Platform v3 & Documentation Tool with open Standard & Certification.

This document is an overview of first-year process to design and create the Made4You platform and is organized as follows:

- Section 1 introduces the project and visually summarizes all the activities carried out concerning both Platform v1 and Documentation tools.
- Section 2 is dedicated specifically to platform, focusing on its preparation by gathering useful information also about target audiences' ideas and expectations, its current layout and next steps to be taken.
- Section 3 presents the documentation with regards to analysis of existing templates, first templates deployed and then the present structure (Documentation Tool v.1).

1.1 OBJECTIVES

The first phase of WP3 Platform & Tooling has the following objectives:

- gather information on current platforms and other systems that people are using, that are similar to the Made4You platform concept;
- understand better who the potential users of the Made4You platform are, their needs, desires and difficulties in approaching platforms with DIY solutions;
- think outside of the box to draw the Made4You platform at its best, designing user interface, taxonomy, solution browsing and overall structure;
- compare existing documentation templates as well as guidelines or supportive tools deployed by current makers' platforms;
- develop and test the Made4You Documentation tool to be used while prototyping solutions in co-design events foreseen in WP1.

1.2 BACKGROUND

Made4You project is about maker communities and the health&care sector. It is embedded within the Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation (CAPSSI) initiative whose goal is to support an environment where communities can develop solutions, ideas or services collaboratively and also share the required design and implementation.

At a first glance, as described in the Grant Agreement (Part B, chapter 1.4.1),
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early growing initiatives related to citizen innovation in the healthcare sector have led to:

- communities of patients and caregivers gathering around dedicated platforms that collect and share needs (often disease-specific) knowledge and concrete bottom-up innovations to cope with symptoms (for example initiatives such as *Patient Innovation*¹);
- inventive professionals of both healthcare and creative sectors making use of innovative tools to tackle societal challenges (for example initiatives such as *MakerNurse*² and *HealthDesignByUs*³);
- Fablabs and makerspaces dealing with health related issues, especially within the framework of projects sustained by EU programmes, and developing solutions published online;
- specialized platforms targeted at a large public audience with an interest in making, whose function is sharing technical documentation and information on the fabrication process of projects, and that generally cover almost all aspects of do-it-yourself production like *Instructables*⁴ or those that are more linked to the engineering domain like *Github*⁵ or *Wevolver*⁶.

In this context - from this very first comparative analysis - some basic and distinctive features of the Made4You platform were defined, as detailed in the table below:

Table 1: Made4You platform features

Made4You platform	
SOLUTIONS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● the main contents are open healthcare solutions ● solutions are for people with disabilities: adults as well as children with special needs or physical limitations ● solutions are mostly codesigned by a team of makers, people with disabilities and healthcare professionals

1 www.patient-innovation.com [Accessed: November 28 2018]

2 makernurse.com [Accessed: November 28 2018]

3 www.healthdesignby.us [Accessed: November 28 2018]

4 www.instructables.com [Accessed: November 28 2018]

5 www.Github.com [Accessed: November 28 2018]

6 www.wevolver.org [Accessed: November 28 2018]

TOOLS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● it has an open source repository for technical documentation ● replicability is supported by documentation ● proper documentation standards is required for successful sharing and adaptation of solutions ● online collaboration tools among users are provided
PLATFORM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Wevolver platform is a key-point of reference ● users are involved in the development of the platform itself ● the platform domain is Careables.org

1.3. TIMELINE

The following timeline visually summarizes the activities carried out for the Platform and Documentation tool described in the next sections:

Figure 1: Timeline

2. Platform

As stated in the project proposal, the Made4You platform goals are:

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- to inspire citizens to become active participants in open healthcare solutions, which are both new co-designed solutions and open grassroots solutions invented by existing communities (like that of e-Nable);
- to support the process of documentation by open standards that not only allow replicability but also guarantee personal safety;
- to enable open knowledge exchange on open source hardware design leveraging on Wevolver platform's structure and features;
- connect users, healthcare professionals, makers and designers to crowdsource solutions so that they can be improved in quality by sharing skills, competences and feedback;
- to use crowdfunding as a sustainable model of finance for the development of specific solutions.

2.1 DESIGN PROCESS

Over the first year implemented activities focused on research to (1) frame the topic, (2) have an overview of the status quo, (3) learn from people and their fresh perspectives and (4) get insights while they approach the tools. To put the process into practice the applied research methods varied on the basis of aims and typology of targets, ranging from makers to healthcare professionals, to care recipients.

Hereby a brief overview:

- *User Field Test*: we involved a TOG healthcare professional and a caregiver of a child with cerebral palsy, observed how they look for things they need on the web and took notes of their obstacles;
- *Baseline Mapping*: existing platforms were studied to analyse their features;
- *Co-design Session*: we planned a brainstorming session with consortium members about Careables.org structure;
- *Survey*: three survey templates were addressed to healthcare professionals, makers and people with disabilities and their caregivers;
- *Interviews*: we talked to four people participating in MakeHealth Live in Eindhoven on October 24th and listened to their direct experience with DIY solutions and maker platforms.

The following sub-sections report in detail the methods and their outcomes.

2.1.1 User Field Test

How can we create a platform for users we don't know? In February 2018 a field-

test on platforms was organised with TOG help and involved a recently hired young female physiotherapist and an energetic woman with a daughter suffering from cerebral palsy. The goals consisted in observing how they search for solutions they need and taking notes of the obstacles encountered while approaching the projects of Wevolver repository.

Table 2: User field test

user field test	
GOALS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● to observe how people search for the solutions they needs ● to have a feedback on what are the obstacles approaching the “documentation for makers”
PARTICIPANTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● C. is 47 years old. She has a 5 years old daughter, with cerebral palsy and she is the one looking after her. Her husband has a good job and she really cares about finding functional and beautiful solutions. Some friends suggested to build what she wasn’t able to find, but she is not a “practical” person. ● S. is a young therapist, quite shy and sensitive. She feels uncomfortable with technologies, but she knows a bit about 3D printing and other digital fabrication technologies, even if she never used them.

Being subjects of “scientific experimentation” might cause anxiety and shyness but little by little the two women felt comfortable and freely interacted, expressed doubts, asked about esoteric terms (“What is BOM?” - a bill of materials) and laughed while scrolling. What we have discovered is a list of things to take into consideration in the next platform development phase.

First of all, language may represent a barrier from two points of view: some people are still struggling to speak and read English and communication requires mediation between varieties of languages (that of healthcare sector and of maker world). Secondly, making appears a matter of “engineers”, dealing with acronyms, files and circuits - but there is no reason to be like this if projects can be comprehensible to anyone and accessible alternatives.

The full descriptions of tests and findings is provided in Annex 1.

2.1.2 Baseline Mapping

Since the Made4You platform is part of a large movement advocating that

everyone can be real “maker of health” - from healthcare professionals to citizens with physical limitations and their caregivers - a broader understanding of what is already available in terms of online community spaces is needed.

Research started in February 2018 and consisted of analysis of existing platforms where people share solutions that are connected to disabilities or impairments. Main evaluation criteria used in drafting the list of platforms were:

- access to solutions;
- nature of solutions (projects versus ideas or concepts);
- “making” nature of solutions, whether they are tricks or DIY objects or more complex and technological devices built with digital fabrication technologies.

When conducting the research, we took into account to two main sources:

- **the state of art presented within the Made4You project proposal’s (Grant Agreement Part B, chapter 1.4.1)**

It stands as a reference point, to illustrate the most influential initiatives with a distinction between communities working on a variety of open healthcare solutions and the existing platforms.

- **Makepedia Project**

In 2016 Makernet consortium, a collaboration among several organizations committed to digital manufacturing applied in humanitarian and social fields, launched a project titled “Makepedia”, that was conceived as a “collaborative platform⁷ for sharing of designs of useful items, enabling people anywhere to make them”. The first phase of Makepedia project consisted of a survey addressed to makers and designers in order to evaluate the current available platforms. Even though the project was archived, the results of this preliminary Makepedia survey (dated from February 2017) are still available online⁸.

Also, we experimented with free search, browsing the Web principally by Google search console/incognito tab and typing semantic keywords in order to enlarge or narrow data while we looked for platforms with solutions for people with physical limitations. The keywords referred to default features of future Careables.org: type of users, of solutions, of platform.

The search was done translating keywords in English, French, German, Italian and Spanish. This is a list of main keywords used and found while processing:

7 <https://github.com/MozillaFoundation/mozfest-program-2016/issues/692> [Accessed: November 29 2018]

8 <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1MZCVMZADNxTkRHWV1Xs79dHMFeDPgGAvs3AAAn7nHW4Q/edit#gid=237476974> [Accessed: November 29 2018]

user related

patient
disabilities
handicapped
plwds (people living with disabilities)
need-knowers
people with special needs
care recipients
caregivers
users as designers
maker
hacker
developer
professional

health domain

health
healthcare
well-being

maker domain

fabrication
digital
3D printing
assistive technologies
wearable

platform - related

collection
platform
repository
catalogue
database

solutions

accessible
for all
codesigned
assistive

engaging
collaborative
applied
shareable
diy
dit (do it together)
diwo (do it with others)

social character

dsi - digital social innovation
digital social problem
tech for good
design for good
user-centred design

On the basis of the three main evaluation criteria, this is the complete list⁹ of analyzed platforms:

Explanation of table fields:

Language: used in the website.

Website ranking: the tool used is www.alexa.com/siteinfo.

Nr of projects: number of projects with tags "health", "disability" and "healthcare".

Complexity: easy/medium/for advanced users only. The choice is taken on the basis of documentation structure and how instructions are described.

Specificity: is the platform devoted to health projects or more generic? The two options are: various categories - only health.

Comments: any notes or considerations (pros and cons)

Table 3: Platforms

Title	Language	Website ranking	Nr of projects	Complexity	Specificity	Comments
Instructables www.instructables.com	English	910	$20 < x < 100$	Medium (format: BOM; steps). Not clear if the explanations are complete (technical drawings are often missing)	various categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Results not always pertinent to health; . download available only for premium users; . No custom menu for instructions/ too long page.
OpenThings www.openthings.wiki	English/ Dutch	not available	< 20	"Easy"	various categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . No projects with health, healthcare tags; . No fields/categories; . Small number of users; . Good version control; . 486 projects in the collection; . Nice layout; . Feedback/updates from users.
Thingiverse www.thingiverse.com	English	1290	> 100	"Easy"	various categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . 450 projects with health, healthcare tags; . Botton: order this printed . Customization apps; . Good interface (menu/feedback from users/good layout); . Thingiverse has a parent consent form to fill in if the user is under 18 years old.

Github github.com	English	70	> 100	For advanced users only.	various categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Signing up is mandatory to enter open source project; . 3492 repository results with health; . Good interface (readable, easy to find sections); . No fixed categories/fields; . Feedback/updates from users.
Wevolver www.wevolver.com	English	725.733	> 100	For advanced users only.	various categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Large community; . Good interface; . No search field; . No fixed menu for instructions; . Feedback form users.
Hackaday www.hackaday.io	English	21.646	> 100	"Easy"	various categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . 160 projects with tag "health"; . single-page long-scrolling webpage but readable and custom menu; . Good interface.
Hackster www.hackster.io	English	16,446	> 100	Medium. Not clear if all the instructions are provided	various categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . 352 projects with "health" tag; . Possibility to buy materials needed for the project; . Coding and file provided; . Building phases maybe not clear (not explained in clear steps).

Duino4projects duino4projects.com	English	283.656	20 < x < 100	Medium. Not clear if the explanations are complete or clear	various categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . More than 20.000 projects (pdf lists available); . Basic layout; . Many tutorials available.
Arduino - Project Hub create.arduino.cc/project-hub	English	2.390	> 100	"Easy"	various categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Many drop-down menus for advanced search (interesting categories); . Huge number of views; . Around 3000 projects; . Lateral menu for readability.
My Mini Factory www.myminifactory.com	various languages	18,269	20 < x < 100	"easy"	various categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Results with tag "health" are not always relevant . Best menu for instructions: readable, clear sections, possibility to download files. It foresees a test-phase before publishing online the projects.
wikifab wikifab.org/wiki/Accueil	various languages	431,446	20 < x < 100	"easy"	various categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . More results in French. instructions specify also estimate of costs. images clarify the various steps.
Youmagine www.youmagine.com	English	80.666	20 < x < 100	Not clear if the explanations are complete - no steps	various categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Results not always pertinent to health; . File available; . Instructions not always complete; . Pro: more than one picture of

						the project; . Featured collections of projects (Pinterest style).
Makers making change www.makersmakingchange.com	English	2.370.031	< 20	"Easy"	only health	. Instructions are detailed in a pdf file; . Photos of the object; . Very accessible projects.
Yeggi www.yeggi.com	English	17,196	> 100	"Easy"	various categories	. Results are not always relevant and connected to health; . Instructions are connected to thingiverse.com or other repositories.
Fabble fabble.cc	English/ Japanese	1,435,382	< 20	In Japanese	various categories	. It seems popular but most of descriptions are in Japanese.
HTH www.hthumanitarians.org/page/toolbox	English	not available	$20 < x < 100$	"easy". The instructions are hosted in other platforms like Github	various categories	. Very basic layout; . Humanitarian projects.
Eddy eddiy.es/doku.php?id=soluciones_segun_discapacidad:soluciones	Spanish	11,375,867	$20 < x < 100$	There's a video explaining the solution but not detailed instructions.	only health	. 56 solutions published. It is a first "careables" version.

Eddy Peru www.eddiy.pe/doku.php?id=vida_independiente:conjunto_de_soluciones_publicadas	Spanish	not available	20 < x < 100		only health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . It's the Eddy version of the platform but developed in Peru.
Appropedia www.appropedia.org	English	225260	20 < x < 100	<p>Not only project but also information on specific topic. When documentation is provided, a description is given, step-by-step guide seem not detailed, link to external platform for further details.</p>	various categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . The Wikipedia interface allows to view the taxonomy behind projects classification; . Navigation is tricky; . Project can have different status (e.g. Not tested yet/prototypes/); . Projects are called OSAT: open source appropriate technologies.
Meviro www.meviro.org	Brazilian/ English	not available	20 < x < 100	<p>The instructions seem easy and clear: materials needed, steps of construction, images</p>	only health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . The website is really interesting, not so far from Eddyburg; . Solutions are maybe simple, frugal.

In addition, the investigation surfaced some insights about this emerging paradigm within the healthcare sector, which were as follows:

Insight: self-managing

People with physical limitations face daily obstacles in their environments and little by little they may become inventive and persistent in discovering means to preserve their independence in personal matters. These DIY solutions have always been out there for “everyone” starting from one of the pioneering examples: that of *Aids to Make You Able: self-help devices and ideas for the disabled* by the occupational therapist Wendy Davis. This book was her thesis work as a graduate student of the University of Alberta, then published in 1977. It is conceived as an incredible catalogue of illustrated solutions covering the basic areas of communication, eating and drinking, dressing, bathroom, household, transportation, leisure and pleasure, sexuality and smoking.

Figure 2: Images from “Aids to Make You Able: self-help devices and ideas for the disabled”

Sure, the Internet has enormously broadened the possibility of sharing solutions created by patients with physical limitations with a wider audience in forms of:

- blogs/personal websites like *Zebreda makes it work*¹⁰ by Zebreda Dunham, *Engineering at home*¹¹ by Cindy or *Handihelp*¹² by Rich Fabend - all with simple but effective adaptations;
- repositories like the Brazilian *Meviro*¹³ with 84 assistive tech projects and

10 www.zebredamakesitwork.com [Accessed: November 29 2018]

11 engineeringathome.org [Accessed: November 29 2018]

12 handihelp.net [Accessed: November 29 2018]

13 www.meviro.org [Accessed: November 29 2018]

the Swedish *Spinalistips*¹⁴, showing “1386 tips from 125 people with spinal cord injuries for assistive devices, adaptations and individually designed solutions”.

Insight: precedents

Searching in different languages drove us to *EDDIY*¹⁵, a Spanish project of 2012 that collected DIY solutions to improve accessibility. The platform had a wiki-based interface and allowed collaborative participation of users. Solutions are mainly frugal: simple but effective adaptations of existing objects and, although some guidelines were provided, documentation of projects was basically poor.

Figure 3: Eddiy homepage

Insight: Matching people

Two recent initiatives are particularly aligned with the Made4You concept: the Canadian *Makers Making Change*¹⁶ by Neil Squire Society (a non-profit organization for people with disabilities), and the German *Match my Maker*¹⁷ by BeAble. Both projects are offering online platforms for makers to volunteer their

14 www.spinalistips.se [Accessed: November 29 2018]

15 eddiy.es [Accessed: November 29 2018]

16 www.makersmakingchange.com [Accessed: November 29 2018]

17 matchmymaker.de/en/ [Accessed: November 29 2018]

time for the specific need of a person with disabilities.

Figure 4: Makers Making Change homepage

Figure 5: Match my Maker homepage

Insight: geographical perspective

Maker movement was born in Usa and still, disruptive innovation produced by culture of making and sharing appears to be more well-established in USA rather than Europe: digital fabrication technologies have entered hospitals - think of the abovementioned *Makernurse*, the community of “nerdy” nurses creating solutions for their patients, or *Makertherapy*¹⁸, the project bringing small makerspaces for hospitalized children - people with health related problems get together online as the success of *Patientslikeme*¹⁹, founded already in 2004, confirms and caring is an educational issue in many universities thanks also to *Design for America*²⁰, the initiative teaming up students in the pursuit of addressing societal challenges.

18 www.makertherapy.com [Accessed: November 29 2018]

19 www.patientslikeme.com [Accessed: November 29 2018]

20 <http://designforamerica.com> [Accessed: November 29 2018]

2.1.3 Co-design session

Following the outcomes of the baseline mapping, OpenDot organized a co-design session on 23rd October 2018 during the consortium meeting in Eindhoven. The intention was to open a free discussion about the Careables platform, its structure, tools and taxonomy and to collecting expectations and visions, before focusing on joint aspects to move forward to next Platform v.2. The participants were all project partners and representatives of the maker world from *Field Ready*²¹ and the *Match my Maker* project interested in the topic.

The chosen methodology leveraged design tools, whose functions are to enable a shared view on key problems/challenges and to creatively produce new functions, uses and meanings. As conceived the co-design session helped to (1) encourage contributions from people with diverse backgrounds, (2) stay focused on selected issues but (3) diverge by considering all possible opportunities and be proactive in terms of ideas, (4) select and leave out features with democratic decision-making and (5) synthesize and decide next steps.

The agenda was organized as follows:

Program	
10.20-13.00	Discussion about Platform core functions
----- lunch -----	
14.00-15.30	Issue#1: Documentation
----- coffee break -----	
15.45-16.45	Issue#2: Taxonomy
16.45-17.00	Introduction to following days co-design session

Figure 6: Programme of co-design session

In particular, concerning the platform, the session defined *Careables.org* functions. The co-design session was guided by a facilitator and used a large printed scheme, enlisting *Careables* objectives as stated in the Grant Agreement. Participants were asked to read the given functions, explore additional extra ones with Post-it notes and then vote for between one and three functions.

21 www.fieldready.org [Accessed: December 28 2018]

1. The careable platform should...

The CAREABLES platform should...
What are the core functions of the platform?

- inspire citizens
- enable knowledge exchange
- connect users (care, healthcare professionals, citizens, caregivers)
- activate participation and allow contributions to the community by caregivers
- support process documentation providing also collaboration tools
- support project team deploying optimal funding models
- foster open grassroots solutions
- simplify the replication of projects by standardised documentation
- be part of a broader ecosystem (collaborate directly, indirect with other actors in the field)
- give indiscriminatory access to open solutions
- support project validation and quality

- 1. Define** what we mean by function
- 2. Discuss** functions
- 3. Add** functions
- 4. Prioritize** functions

Tools:
Printed scheme and post-it

Figure 7: Careables platform

The result was participatory and colorful brainstorming. While it was in some ways predictable that documentation would have been the most voted Careables function (*priority 1: simplify the replication of projects by standardised documentation*), surprisingly by choosing to *inspire citizens* as priority 2 the participants declare they expect the platform to create value - in terms of empowering people with disabilities - of engendering greater empathy, of facilitating better person-centred care, something to take into account in next steps.

2.1.4 Survey

Within the process of designing a platform, personas are a key to conceptualizing users (who we're building it for and why). A persona is, in fact, a fictional but realistic portrait of target users and it is helpful to build a user-centric platform for the following reasons:

- understanding people concerns, goals, motivations, requirements;
- segmenting user types;
- summarizing user research data;
- keeping in check people concerns, goals, motivations, requirements while proceeding with each design decision.

In order to build personas, authentic data are needed. User research was based on an online survey. This tool was selected because it can be distributed widely, it can easily collect useful feedback from a large number of respondents, and it is relatively objective and neutral.

In designing the survey, three main aspects were counted:

- Careables.org target users:
 - people with healthcare needs and their carers
 - healthcare professionals
 - makers, engineers, and designers
- The goal of acquiring knowledge from the three user groups about their behaviors towards health-care related topics and the Internet.
- A draft of Careables.org user-experience design (represented below).

Figure 8: Careables UX

Together with ZSI, three surveys were prepared with the following structures (see Annex 2 for Survey templates):

Table 4: Survey templates

survey templates	
MAKERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● maker platforms: to learn directly from experts ● finding Careables: to learn how to best tag Careables to make them search and findable in the community of makers ● creating Careables: to learn experiences about

	building Careables <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● co-designing Careables: to learn experiences or ideas about participatory projects ● about you: to outline who are the users
HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● health care devices: to learn experiences with searching for and using health care devices ● Careables: to learn experiences about suggesting and searching for Careables ● digital fabrication technologies: to learn about experiences with these tools ● Careables platform: to collect input in order to build a useful platform for Careables ● co-designing Careables: to learn experiences or ideas about participatory projects ● about you: to outline who are the users
PEOPLE WITH HEALTHCARE NEEDS AND THEIR CARERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● health care devices: to learn experiences with searching for and using health care devices ● Careables: to learn experiences about suggesting and searching for Careables ● Careables platform: to collect input in order to build a useful platform for Careables ● co-designing Careables: to learn experiences or ideas about participatory projects ● about you: to outline who are the users

The surveys were distributed through consortium channels and networks. Furthermore, the survey for makers was shared within FabLab community and the survey for Italian healthcare professionals (a translated version was provided) was promoted by AITO - Associazione Italiana Terapisti Occupazionali.

The response rate was good:

Makers: 99

Healthcare professionals: 74

People with healthcare needs and their carers: 26

A more detailed analysis of surveys results will be conducted and used to build Careables personas. Some valuable insights are highlighted below:

MAKER SURVEY: highlights

Figure 9: Makers and platforms

Figure 10: Preferred features for makers

Figure 11: Co-designing and platforms - makers opinions

HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONAL SURVEY: highlights

careables.org

Figure 12: Preferred features for healthcare professionals

Figure 13: Platforms interface for healthcare professionals

Figure 14: Co-designing and platforms - healthcare professionals opinions

PEOPLE WITH HEALTHCARE NEEDS SURVEY: highlights

careables.org

Figure 15: Preferred features for people with needs

Figure 16: Platforms interface for people with needs

Figure 17: Co-designing and platforms - people with needs' opinions

2.1.5 Interviews

During MakeHealth Live!, the event organised by project partner Waag at Dutch Design Week Eindhoven in October 2018 about co-designing solutions for health challenges, we took some time to interview a sample of its participants, representatives of healthcare sector, design fields and maker world. The intention was to have the chance to get to a deeper level of understanding of needs and obstacles with both sharing platforms and, generally, projects for social good. The applied methodology was based on inspiring book *The Mom Test: How to talk to customers & learn if your business is a good idea when everyone is lying to you* by Rob Fitzpatrick. Therefore, we preferred open-ended questions in order to collect honest and valuable feedback from people's direct experiences and problems rather than general opinions or affirmations.

The interview focused on these questions, following the structure of the survey:

- tell us something about you
- are you familiar with platforms like *Instructables*? Which features do you appreciate the most? Any difficulties?
- have you ever created a solution for people with disabilities? Can you explain to us the purposes, motivations and process?

The anonymized reports are given below:

S. - Maker, Male

Background

He used to work for "open source" then he approached the healthcare field through an organization.

Platforms

As a user, he is interested in the final product as it looks and he doesn't care about customization: he want to open the file or the project page and immediately see it. As a designer he want to know the final cost, all the precise steps and be able to customize pieces of file. It is important to have the "solution history" as not to repeat errors.

Creating solutions

He finds difficulties in the co-design process, especially in collaborating with makers because:

- the project must be functional to their own interests and fit their workflow and intentions ("What do I get from this?")
- the workflow between them and users should be constant;
- it is necessary to present a problem in order to engage them.

B. - Graphic Designer, Female

Background

Graphic designer with a background in therapy for children with disabilities. She switched to graphic design because she couldn't find job in the healthcare sector. As a graphic designer she's trying to work in the healthcare sector.

Platforms

She used platforms such as *YouVo* (volunteering with NGOs) to look for projects to collaborate with for free or with minimum contribution.

Features of platforms she generally appreciates:

- to feel a human presence behind the various processes;
- NGOs have to take action to follow the work and select collaborators;
- e-mails inform about news related to personal interests;
- there is a platform contact person.

J. - Designer, Female

Background

She is a student of industrial design from USA in exchange.

Platforms

She uses platforms such as *Instructables* but mostly to see the method that people apply. While carrying out university projects, she tries not to copy whole projects as she is interested in understanding methods and steps by herself. She uses platforms mainly for inspiration and research.

When conducting research on users or in specific areas, she finds useful to have a synthesis of problems and errors people already encountered. This is to avoid waste of time.

Design for America provides tools to document all the steps of the process (texts, images, videos); she uses it for research and to upload projects.

Platform that she appreciates less: *WikiHow* as it seems very fake and superficial.

Platform that appreciates more: *Instructables* because it is young and playful.

Creating solutions

She has done some projects on the subject of healthcare like apps and "medical technologies".

W. - Occupational Therapist Student, Female

Background

She helps people with disabilities to perform difficult daily actions. She is in her first year and has never had any field experience.

Platforms

Platforms used in healthcare sector are neutral sites. She would like selected content, sites where you can find affordable products, no forum because people talk randomly and there is no doctor behind.

Creating solutions

There is a body in the Netherlands that distributes certified devices but the attitude of her professional category is also to make objects from scratch (official certified objects are too difficult to modify).

Two difficulties:

- she wouldn't even know from where to start to design a Careable. She vaguely says that she would ask support from people she knows. She would turn to a developer for a possible idea.
- she can't visualize the possible outcome and also translate the idea into a product (or prototype) because she doesn't know where to find materials and tools.

2.2 HOW THE PLATFORM IS

To create the best possible user experience we decided to use two systems:

System 1: WordPress

A WordPress installation that provides visitors of the online part of Careables with an introduction and basic knowledge about the project.

WordPress is a free and open-source content management system. The system has been widely adopted because of its easy user interface. In addition it is a tool most people in the consortium are already familiar with, which allows anyone to add, or update information, irregardless of their location.

WordPress provides a calendar for events, a news page, and a featured solutions page where we highlight popular solutions that have been shared by the community. These featured solutions were chosen based on our experience of general interest. Having worked closely with a maker community certain topics are more popular than others. These topics have been highlighted on the WordPress page to gather interest and get a visitor to the Careables collaboration platform.

System 2: Wevolver

The WordPress installation is a gateway to the repository where stakeholders can access documentation of hardware solutions using the documentation tool developed by consortium member Wevolver.

There is a distinct difference between the two tools: WordPress is for managing basic functionalities around communication (blog posts, events, basic background information about the Careables project), while the Wevolver software is for the actual sharing and collaborating on the technological solutions, and the communication around those solutions.

We will keep using the WordPress installation in the future for communication and dissemination purposes. So the main focus is on the Wevolver repository since that is where the actual innovation and community building will take place.

2.2.1 Platform structure

The WordPress platform is structured with different access rights:

- some users have full administration rights, meaning they can override all other consortium members to create new accounts, add features, and edit the design;
- some users have only content rights, which means they can only add

pages (in the future we might also give these rights to people outside the consortium such as project partners or external individuals, who want to share their knowledge and/or experience on the Careables blog, or want to add events to the calendar).

The WordPress structure of the platform is as following:

Homepage: the landing page contains all the sections a visitor could access via the links in the top of the page. This gives them a clear overview of what the project entails, and shows directly what sections can be accessed.

The sections are:

- *News:* Blog posts about current news related to the topics Careables is involved in.
- *Events:* Calendar with upcoming relevant events, written down in an elaborate way. Includes dates, venue, organiser, and links to external websites.
- *Discover projects:* Direct link to the discover list with currently shared solutions.
- *Share a project:* Guides the visitor to the sign-up page where they can start sharing a project.
- *About Careables:* More information about who Careables is and what it stands for, as well as more information about the consortium.

The next version that is currently in production enables the following features:

Table 5: Platform features

platform functions	
A VISITOR TO:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● browse public projects ● register as a user ● read public discussion threads ● browse projects based on tags ● use the search functionality ● look at public user profiles
A USER (A REGISTERED PERSON) TO:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● add a public or private project ● use the documentation tool and template for easy project entry ● upload files ● create a public profile to establish an online identity

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● browse public projects ● read public discussion threads ● post and comment on discussion threads ● browse projects based on tags ● follow tags ● follow projects and get a notification email when the project gets an update ● use the search functionality ● look at public user profiles
--	--

2.2.2 Repository

The project database is hosted by Wevolver. This system allows people to browse through solutions, and to use a search feature to look for a more specific project. Users are able to:

- **Access the documentation:** A visitor enter a project page and can read a description of the project, the motivation, about the team, and any other content created by a project creator.
- **Download the files needed to reproduce the technologies:** Each project contains all the necessary files to develop the solutions documented such as 3D-files, images, and videos. This enables people to download files and use digital fabrication machines to reproduce them
- **Interact with the community:** Each project has a comment section where visitors can read discussions, ask questions, give feedback, or ask for help. Comments are linked to user accounts which enables people to learn more about the people engaging with them.
- **Learn about community members:** Each user has a unique profile page where others can learn about their identity both on Careables, as well as outside Careables. Others will be able to see what projects and tags people are following, see their most recent activity, and visit their personal websites or social media channels.
- **Ask questions:** A registered user can also engage in the comment section by posting questions. When others respond to their question they will get an email notification to let them know someone has answered their question.
- **Answer questions:** A registered user can reply to questions and give answers.
- **Give feedback:** A registered user can “reply” to projects and give feedback on shared solutions using the same comment section.
- **Follow tags:** A registered user can follow tags of interest. For example;

following the tag “bionics” will enable email notifications when a new project with this tag has been shared.

- **Follow project:** A registered user can follow a project. This triggers a system that sends them an email when an existing project gets updated, or people have left a comment or question in the project documentation.
- **Share solutions and document work in an organized manner:** A registered user can share their solutions leveraging our custom onboarding template.
- **Use an automated template system:** A template that takes a registered user through a series of questions asking for context, as well as files or images. This helps the user to effectively share their work in a structured manner.
- **Use a version control system:** The version control system enables other people to work on the projects, yet if mistakes are made, the creator of the project is able to reverse the documentation back in time, restoring previous versions of his or her work.

All the features mentioned above have already been implemented.

2.3 PLATFORM DESIGN DECISIONS (DESIGN BRIEF)

The design of the platform is based on the description written in the Grant Agreement - Part B, the field tests, the personal experience and competence of designers involved (in particular Opendot’s and Wevolver’s team), the baseline mapping, the research and the co-design session done in Eindhoven.

What has been made is a starting point that aims mainly at creating a brief for the future development, detailing a set of features and goals, validated by a preliminary evaluation to reduce the risk of future feasibility issues.

2.3.1 Shared platform brief

The following report is a synthesis of the results of the first twelve months - in particular ideas that emerged during co-design session in Eindhoven - and has been reviewed by all the partners of the consortium, so it can be considered a shared platform brief.

Process, method, and tools used during the co-design session are described in 2.1.3, while all the other activities implemented such as preliminary user tests are described in 2.1.1, 2.1.2 and 2.1.4.

All the suggestions previously collected were consolidated into the template that was used during the co-design session held in Eindhoven in October 2018 for evaluation by Made4You consortium.

Figure 18: Co-design session for the platform

Note

The results have been organized from the most important to the least important. Some features received no votes (hypothesis on the motivation will be provided), but this doesn't mean that they have been classified as less urgent or impactful. Other features have been added to the list by consortium partners based on Made4You experiences over the first year.

FEATURES THAT WERE VOTED (PRIORITY BASED ORDER)

- **1 - Simplify the replication of projects by standardized documentation:** documentation will be a central part of the project analyzed later in point 3 and the first objective of the platform is to help the creation and replication of Careables.
 - *Facilitate user experience as soon as possible:* implies the importance of being attractive and known to all target users (makers, healthcare professionals and care recipients).
- **2 - Inspire citizens:** the engagement is different if the user is personally interested or professionally interested. Both levels will be present in the same area of the platform to facilitate cross-fertilization between the groups and languages. It emerged from the Careables Meet-up (see D.1.1 Engagement strategy and documentation of events) that a positive

empowering feeling is created when different targets learn from each other or develop empathy for each other.

- *Telling stories*: useful to develop empathy and engage the target maker user. It also helps outreach and makes healthcare professionals and care recipients more keen to experiment and confident in the potential of the process.
 - *Influencer marketing\performance marketing*: a more traditional approach could involve marketing strategies based on influencer or performances of a Careable. There are people facing physical limitation that have a large number of followers on social media and could reach a very sensitive group of people. Data collected by studies on DIY healthcare solutions could also help to motivate researchers, companies, and healthcare professionals to contribute and take a Careable to the next level.
 - *Differentiate between complete and incomplete projects*: it is important to create spaces where people can contribute. Clear labelling of the tasks that must be completed or list of possible contributions could be an entry points for new users.
- **3 - Connect users**: a fundamental consequence of the development of a Careable is the creations of a working group and the connections established among members involved. It creates local groups among unconnected communities, impacting users' social needs.
 - *Create community*: both offline local community (during the Careables meetups or around work benches) and online community thanks to the platform.
 - *Connect with communities besides users*: local communities of makers, healthcare professionals, and care recipients are often weakly connected, because they attend different places, events, activities, training programs, etc.
 - *Facilitate connections between users/families with professionals*:_the platform could help this match by supporting team creation, in particular, thanks to possible partnerships with other ongoing funded projects that share Made4You's vision.
 - **4 - Support process documentation providing also collaboration tools** (This point will be detailed in Section 3.2)
 - **4 - Be part of a broader ecosystem**: as already discussed, open production and distribution models are based on highly interconnected ecosystems. An important project goal is to find those valuable

connections and develop mutually beneficial collaborations (in particular as a roll-out strategy).

- *Target nearby fabrication hubs, similar relevant platforms and online services:* the production capability is not limited to FabLabs, (although it is the most coherent and flexible production network existing globally) and global suppliers, networks of producers, etc. could be key partners.
- *Communicate related events to show that the possible connections are not limited to production or to commercial partnerships:* It is important to be known to leverage communities and people inside organizations.
- **4. Give nondiscriminatory access to open solutions:** openness should be an objective of the platform, not just because of a license on its code, but as a philosophy and a design approach.
 - *Different languages:* even if English usage is growing, it is still a barrier for people that don't use it daily. If translating all content is a struggle, it's important to identify the key areas of the platform, that need to be made available in other languages.
 - *Accessible globally:* Made4You has a geographical reference target within the European Union borders, but it keeps the ambition to spread and have an impact internationally, in particular in places where healthcare systems are less effective. Often such places have limited Internet access and therefore the objectives include keeping the platform accessible from a variety of contexts, being mobile ready and allowing some features (i.e. the Documentation Tool) to work even when temporarily offline
 - *Freely accessible:* one of the objectives is to integrate a technical solution that allows accessibility for as many categories of people with physical limitations as possible.
- **5. Support project validation and quality:** this is crucial, particularly when considering new regulations on medical devices: Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices (see Deliverable D6.1 chapter 4.3.2.2). No planned actions have yet been set. As a transitional solution, Careables will focus on solutions that are not considered medical devices. Documentation will show if the project has been co-designed or approved by a healthcare professional.

FEATURES THAT RECEIVE NO VOTES

- **Activate participation:** user engagement is a continuous challenge but both proposed activities here do not impact the architecture of the platform.
 - Awards (categorized by different aspects such as price, idea, usage...);
 - Involvement of notable partners (“Careables for IDEO”).
- **Enable knowledge exchange:** a cornerstone of the project so all four proposed activities here are considered “included by default”, and usually refer more to the hosted content rather than platform structure itself.
 - Capture knowledge
 - Provide knowledge on how to create and release Careables
 - Provide knowledge on how to run and facilitate Careables events
 - Forum
- **Support project teams to deploy optimal funding models:** sustainability of the platform is not a trivial matter, and some preliminary strategies have been discussed. However, this relates more to the content and partnerships than the platform structure.
 - Provide lists of foundations that have already funded projects.
 - Provide information about grants.
- **Foster open, grassroots solutions:** considering that the main aim of the project is to collect, document and share open solutions for health & care, many aspects here are “included by default” and is more an engagement strategy goal than a platform feature.
 - Support easy access to new users.

FEATURES THAT HAVE BEEN ADDED

Note: These features have been added during the co-design sessions and therefore, has not been voted and commented, but they collected general support from all the partners

+ **Raise awareness:** it impacts mainly the dissemination strategy, but it also helps to balance the weights of the parts in the homepage\landing page. If the goal is to impact more on the awareness, than the contents developed and shown shouldn't be limited to the Careables, and should include personal stories, products that don't match with the Careable definition, and so on.

+ **Sell and buy Careables:** an economical system related to the production of Careables has been considered fundamental in the sustainability of the model. It is too early to define a proper model but some beta test will be deployed, both to evaluate possible roll-out strategies and to create a higher engagement for

professionals (healthcare and makers). A Careable, co-designed with a visually impaired user, has been replicated few times (6 pieces has been produced so far) and sold by the user himself. At the same time, ways to involve active, sensitive people must be put in place: donations, crowdfunding, etc. need to be tested and the platform has to be ready to integrate it when needed.

2.3.2 Next Steps

Based on these results, the new platform structure is outlined as follows:

Table 6: Next platform structure

list of request	possible feature	priority (0-5)	attended impact	implementation complexity
1. Simplify the replication of projects by standardised documentation				
Facilitate users' life as soon as possible	Simple platform structure, diffuse platform support (tips and/or walkthrough, FAQ), research suggestions and filters, clear and fast reachable tools to connect users with professional users	4	4	2
2. Inspire citizens				
Telling stories	blog, stories section, newsletter	4	3	2
Influencer marketing \ performance marketing	Not a platform feature (marketing strategy)	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
Differentiate between done and not done projects	check box in documentation header	3	2	1
3. Connect users				
Create community	meetups maps\visualization of makers and labs	2	3	4

Connect communities besides users	newsletter\stories. Not platform feature but outreach and marketing	3	2	3
Facilitate connections between users/families with professionals and support team creation	Not platform feature (partner project like Matchmymaker)	2	4	4
(4. Support process documentation providing also collaboration tools - see chapter 3)				
4. Be part of a broader ecosystem				
Address to nearby fabrication hubs, similar relevant platforms and online services	partner page, API, vertical integrations (i.e. buy through shapeways)	3	3	3
Communicate related events	(to be identified)			
4. Give indiscriminately access to open solutions				
Different languages	automatic translation/ crowdsourced/edited translation	1	4	5
Accessible globally	tech optimization	3	3	4
Barrier free accessibility	optimization for accessibility / (customization on the user profile?)	4	4	5
5. Support project validation and quality				
Participation of a healthcare professional in the team	check box in documentation header	4	4	2

More advanced validation process	integration of contents, API	3	5	5
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Moreover, as detailed in deliverable D 6.1, protection of individuals and their personal data should be a key principle to follow for the next development phases of Careables.org. It is therefore important that within the platform there will be a dedicated (and easily retrievable) place where information over the processing of personal data is provided.

3. Documentation

Industrial solutions are disseminated using standardized, centralized, mass production and expensive, aggressive and marketing-oriented distribution. The diffusion of Careables takes a different approach of openly-sharing distributed, personalized solutions and focusing on users. Documentation is therefore a tool to facilitate the distribution in a community-oriented open production system.

The focus on Documentation Tool started with research and the baseline mapping, which underlined the nonexistence of a standardized documentation format for making things; a format that is designed for non-technical people, with information organized hierarchically, to allow different levels of detailing.

Based on the experience of project partners, a set of features for documentation has been defined as follows:

- **Accessible:** the largest possible group of users should be able to access, search, find, understand, replicate and use the documented Careables;
- **Open:** to support people to be open, share and improve the information shared about the Careables;
- **Standard:** a standardized structure to documentation will engage users (healthcare and makers) and encourage adoption;
- **Easy:** as a guide, if there is a choice between two possible options, the choice that simplifies the user journey is to be preferred.

3.1 DESIGN PROCESS

In parallel with the research on platforms, research on documentation was conducted with the purposes of (1) analyzing existing documentation templates in use, (2) getting feedback from users, (3) outlining possible supportive tools to be provided and (4) drafting templates and questioning them in a collaborative way. The methodology mirrors that of the platform research and consists of:

- *Baseline Mapping:* the study of documentation templates used by other platforms had the aim of informing a first comprehensive Careables documentation draft;
- *User Field Test:* we structured a workshop about documentation, asking participants to read carefully some documentation of solutions and to develop a new documentation interface;
- *Co-Design Session:* the event in Eindhoven with consortium members was used also to discuss the latest documentation template;
- *Survey:* we prepared and sent out three survey templates addressed to healthcare professionals, makers and people with disabilities and their

caregivers.

The following sub-sections illustrate the implemented activities.

3.1.1 Baseline mapping

The research consisted of the analysis of documentation templates given by existing online platforms. It looked at both online visible projects pages, their structures and interfaces and at on the back-end form where users can enter their documentation (accessed generally by logging in).

The research led to these results:

(a) From *Instructables* to *Thingiverse*, existing platforms do tend to standardize the documentation of projects by creating structured forms available to users. The purpose is twofold: on one hand, since documentation is a challenge, having a path for users is extremely helpful, especially for those who are absolute beginners; on the other hand documenting is a matter of clarity and technical accuracy and an easy documentation template is a “competitive advantage” for platforms.

(b) In this context *Wevolver* documentation is an exception: a free white page with no pre-filled form fields for users to use. This might cause blank page syndrome but *Wevolver* users (who are mainly engineers) are used to documenting and keeping track of processes, and so such a non-structure simplifies rather than frightens. From the perspective of visitors, the uneven documentation may be a problem because project pages vary considerably in terms of quality and quantity of information.

(c) The Japanese *Fabble* makes a compromise since documentation can be in two formats: memo is a free-form notation for any type of information while recipe is a crafting process arranged in chronological order (a more traditional step-by-step description).

(d) Since documenting is difficult, most of platforms support the process with guidelines or tutorials, such as *Best Practices, Read, in one page, what every Wikifab project should have!*²² by *Wikifab*, or *How to create a high-quality project tutorial* by *Hackster*.

22 wikifab.org/wiki/Wikifab:Best_practices [Accessed: December 6 2018]

(e) Also, videos and photos are a key part of project documentation, to explain visually how a Careable is made and how it looks. However the mapped platforms do not foresee tutorials for videos but instead favor taking good images. These were:

- Instructables;
- Wikifab;
- Hackster;
- Fable which also has a presentation mode that generates step-by-step version of instructions.

On the basis of these results, two further steps were taken:

Exploration of video documentation

We explored video documentation, finding inspirations and/or taking notes from user feedback. The findings are given below:

Project Overview Video Examples

- [Precious Plastic - Introduction](#)
- [OpenROV v2.7](#)
- [PLEN Project](#)
- [Introducing FarmBot Genesis](#)

Promotional Video Example: [FarmBot Genesis Promotional](#)

Promotional videos for sharing on social media should aim to be around 60-seconds with introduction videos on the project itself no longer than 3-minutes for maximum engagement.

Assembly Guide Video Example: [Precious Plastic - Shredder](#)

The feedback received from *Wevolver* users on Precious Plastic was that following the video instructions in real-time was too difficult; users were required to rewind and pause the video, usually on their smartphone. Users wanted written step-by-step assembly instructions to support the video.

Assembly Guide Video Example: [Exiii - Assembling Hackberry](#)

Exiii had a similar approach to Precious Plastic but relied less on verbal communication and more on explicitly showing how the device can be assembled using both 3D design animations and live action video, without written instructions. This worked very well to help Exiii, who are based in Japan, overcome issues in regards to language barriers, but again, users requested written step-by-step assembly instructions to support the video.

Draft of the documentation template

Using the comparison of different documentation templates, we outlined the first Careables.org documentation tool (see Table 6, below). It is basically constructed by migrating all the pre-filled form fields of existing templates and adapting their description lines into the form of questions.

Table 7: Careables draft documentation tool

TITLE OF THE PROJECT + images	
Description	Brief text (max x characters)
	Date of creation / updates
	Difficulty level (top-down menu)
	Cost
	Video presenting project
	About authors - different categories
	Website author/project
	Licenses (properly described)
How the project works	Why you made it?
	What is it doing?
	(Features) What the object is?
What you need	What to buy
	Tools needed
	Files to download
	Can i buy it? (for how much?)
Instructions	Steps (pre organized steps)
	Explanatory images/videos
	How long does it take?
	Ask for help!!! --- point out a problem
Files	Download
Images	(Object's images also by other users)
Tags	
Feedback	Star rating
	Comments
	Updated versions by users (versioning)
Interesting objects for you	

3.1.2 User Field Test

On 16th March 2018 we held a workshop entitled *Why and how to make documentation, the importance of building communities around ideas* at Milano Luiss Hub for Makers and Students in Milan. The aims were:

- to share our knowledge about maker platforms;
- to analyze a project's documentation;
- to draft from scratch a documentation template.

The fourteen participants (aged 20-50, mainly students) were asked to select one platform presented during the introduction and analyze the documentation of projects, writing down comments and suggestions. The results were:

General comments

- A project's description sometimes is too short, with few details.
- A project's description sometimes is too long and lacks visual explanation or graphic images.
- Project assembly is not always understandable; sometimes there is no step by step description.
- Coding/electronics are not always understandable for "common" users.
- Too many technical words (e.g. BOM or remix it) and details (e.g. .md file format).
- A project's functions, how a project works is not always detailed.

Suggestions

- It is interesting to have always video presentation of the project: how to use the project and how to make it.
- It is important to have a photo of real object vs a render.
- It would be interesting to know where to print material / where you can buy materials, not only electronics components but also plastic, silicone etc.
- It would be important to have a discussion section with comments and feedback from other users.
- Text should have always graphics to clarify.
- Include a "testing" section, how can I know if the project works properly?

Possible additions to the pre-filled form fields of the documentation template

- Price
- Materials needed (e.g. what kind of plastic?/What kind of 3D printer?)
- Construction time (e.g. how long does it take to 3D print components?)
- Object's sizes/ measurements /dimension.

3.1.3 Codesign Session

In October 2018 OpenDot organized a co-design session during the consortium meeting in Eindhoven (see section 2.1.3.) with the objective of creatively

discussing issues related to the platform (particularly taxonomy and features) and to discuss documentation in some detail.

The process was guided by a facilitator and used a large printed scheme reproducing the current documentation template developed by Wevolver.

2. Documentation

Project Documentation
Review and open questions

Automatic translation? Offline edit and upload? Same format for all targets?

id	type	name	Mandatory? optional? visible?
		1. Basic	
X	X	Thumbnail	
X		Title	
X		Description (up to 1000 characters max)	
		Private / Private / Public	
		2. Project Overview	
X	X	Youtube URL / Banner image	
X	X	Summary (short image)	
X	X	Goals (short image)	
X	X	Specifications/ initial requirements (short image)	
X	X	Timeline (short image)	
X	X	Tools (short image)	
		Category (list): - programming - hardware - business - other	
X	X	3. Process	
X	X	Process steps (as needed)	

- 1. Documentation test:** open discussion on the different areas of the documentation format.
- 2. Add/modify** elements
- ... Respond** to open questions

Tools:
Printed scheme and notes

Figure 19: Co-designing about documentation

The process consisted in: reading carefully the current fields of the structure; evaluating clarity and thoroughness of the single form fields; understanding template's adaptability to eventual projects with reference to e.g. various range of complexity or different development stages; adding extra features e.g. supportive tools.

interface but also possible documentation tools.

These are the results:

Figure 21: Priority given to interfaces in responses from healthcare professionals

Figure 22: Priority given to interfaces in responses from people with disabilities

3.2 DOCUMENTATION TOOLS

The first version of the documentation tool has been built. This tool enables project creators - people who share their designs on Careables - to follow a set of questions which they fill in, as well as asking them to add files. Following and finishing the steps in this template help the creator to share clear documentation of their work. After creating their project with the template, they have full flexibility to add, or extract content.

3.2.1 Structure

The actual version of the template include the following fields:

- *Project profile image*: This serves as the main image of the project. This image shows up when people browse projects in the Careables project list.
- *Project title*: Short name of the project.
- *Description*: We use the description as the project pitch in the discover list on Careables. This pitch is also the meta description we submit to Google as indexation.
- *Video URL (enables video content in the documentation)*: A user can share a link to a Youtube URL. This URL will generate a clickable image preview which triggers the video when clicked on.
- *Summary*: How would you explain your project?: A short description which helps a user to get a quick overview of the solution in order to access it's value for him/her. A good description also helps the Careables algorithm to index the project in it's internal search functionality, as well as with the indexation on external search engines.
 - (option to add images) From experience, we know engagement goes up drastically when project images are added. This feature enables users to upload project images which will be automatically uploaded to the project documentation.
- *Goal*: What does this project aim to accomplish?: This question helps a user to assess if the solution might have an impact for their problem as well.
 - (option to add images)
- *Specifications*: Did the project need to meet any requirements? Are there certain rules, regulations, or quality standards the project needs to meet?
 - (option to add images)
- *Roadmap (optional)*: What future work is planned? What version of the project is the current version which has been shared? Are new iterations planned?
 - (option to add images)

- **Team:** Who worked on this project? In this space, the person documenting the project can specifically mention the people who were involved in the project. This gives the reader an opportunity to directly contact specific people, for example, the healthcare professional involved, or a maker which created a version of the project.
 - (option to add images)

After going through these steps the user presses the “Create Project” button which generates a document based on the input that has just been described. This is an open, and editable document which can be freely iterated on.

3.2.2 Sections: how to fill in

DISCOVER START PROJECT SEARCH WEVolver STAFF

CREATE PROJECT

BASICS

Thumbnail:
 At least 400x120 pixels

Title:

Description: Pitch your project in 70 characters or less.

Privacy:
 Public
 Anyone can see this project. You choose who can modify it.
 Private
 You choose who can see and modify this project.

PROJECT OVERVIEW

Youtube URL: Do you have a project video?

No video? [Start your overview with a banner image instead](#)

Summary: How would you explain your project?

Add Images to Project Summary
JPG, PNG or GIF • 2148 file limit

Goal: What does this project aim to accomplish?

Add Images to Project Goal
JPG, PNG or GIF • 2148 file limit

Specifications: Did the project need to meet any requirements?

Add Images to Technical Specifications
JPG, PNG or GIF • 2148 file limit

Roadmap (optional): What future work is planned?

Add Images to Project Roadmap
JPG, PNG or GIF • 2148 file limit

Team: Who worked on this project?

Add Images to Team
JPG, PNG or GIF • 2148 file limit

CREATE

Figure 23: Create a project

To share a project on the Careables platform a user needs to go through the following steps.

A user signs up for a new account with their email address.

Add first, last name, and include a password for future login and profile identity on the platform. After these steps, a user is ready to start a project.

To document a project the user goes through all the steps which are explained in section 4.3.1. In these steps, the user can also decide if he/she wants the project to be public or private. This option has been implemented to offer the user time to document their work privately before sharing it publicly with the community.

After these steps the user hits the “create” button which creates a document that shows all the data entered in the template in a structured way.

From here on the user can start iterating on the documentation and inviting team members to collaborate with.

The user is now also able to add assembly guides. These step by step instructions show a visitor to the project how the solution can be assembled.

The user can add any file that’s needed to create complete documentation. This includes images, videos, PDFs with deeper knowledge, and even 3D files for digital manufacturing.

Finally, the project page also enables the user, collaborators, and visitors to “clone” the project. This enables them to create a direct copy of the project, both online and on their desktop.

See Annex 3 for further details on documentation overview project documentation.

3.2.3 Supportive tools

The main supporting tool is the project template. This template guides a user through the entire documentation process by asking questions, and asking for videos and images. Following these guidelines will enable the user to create a clear and accessible project documentation.

On Careables.org a new user can find an “Instruction” page. This page explains everything that needs to be collected, and/or in place before he/she starts documenting their project. This helps people to understand what it means to share a “Careable project” and it makes the onboarding and sharing of a solution much easier. From this page onwards, we will also link to three model projects in order to have a benchmark project that a user can refer to and learn from.

There is a separate desktop application that enables people to synchronize an

entire project to their local computer. This enables team members of a project to work on a project locally and synchronize it with the online version of their project. Doing so ensures each team member always has the latest version on their computer and guarantees that due to the online repository each mistake that is made can be reversed.

3.3 DOCUMENTATION DESIGN DECISIONS (DESIGN BRIEF)

The design of the documentation template and process is based on the description wrote in the grant agreement - Part B, the field tests, the personal experience of the makers involved (in particular Opendot's, Fablab Berlin's, Waag's, TOG's and Wevolver's team), the baseline mapping, the research and the co-design session held in Eindhoven.

What has been made, is a starting point that aims mainly to create a brief for the future development, detailing a set of features and goals, validated by a preliminary evaluation to reduce the risk of future feasibility issues.

3.3.1 Shared Documentation Brief

The following report is a synthesis of the results of the first 12 months (in particular it includes the preliminary user tests and the co-design session in Eindhoven) and has been reviewed by all the partner of the consortium, therefore it can be considered a shared documentation template and process brief.

Process, method, and tools used during the co-design session are described in 4.2.

All the suggestions previously encountered, has been collected in the template used during the co-design session and evaluated by all the partner of the consortium. Every aspect has been discussed considering both the impact and the development complexity.

During the discussion about the platform in the co-design session, a part of the conversation focussed on the documentation (marked as "4."), and it will be discussed and detailed here:

Results from platform co-design session

- **Support process documentation providing also collaboration tools:**
Every online platform that allows multiple users to work on the same file, uses some form of versioning control. Even if the most famous one is Github, it definitely doesn't classify as the most accessible and friendly. On

the opposite side of the spectrum, even Google Docs allows some sort of versioning and editing control, but it has limited or no capability to apply these features to not Google's native files. Considering the potential complexity of the projects documented and the variety of files and formats used, the documentation template needs a quite advance versioning system that should be totally invisible for non-technical final users.

- *As simple as possible*: a large part of the Platform users will be non-technical users. Based on preliminary results and previews experiences of the partners, a too articulated interface, a sector-specific language, and excessive acronyms discourage a large part of the audience. The look and feel of the documentation should be more similar to a cooking recipe, than a maintenance manual.
- *Enable interaction for creating and improving*: to animate an online community it's important to allow different levels of engagement and impact of the intervention. Because of this both new projects and modification\customizations of existing ones are important and need to be tracked.
- *Split documentation into "research" and "final recipe"*: documentation has two different goals, one is to keep track of the progress done and share information within the working group, the second is to guide other people to replicate a Careable following its "recipe".
- *Step by step guide*: after evaluating different formats, the easier for non-technical users is the "step by step" one. It is a common, widely used format that looks familiar to the larger part of the audience
- *Provide structure but allow freedom*: even if the non-technical users prefer to have a very standardized structure, familiar and recognizable, some projects are difficult to document this way. The format will preserve the possibility for expert users to edit the structure if needed
- *Support licence decision (open by default)*: based on the feedback from technical and non-technical users, choosing a license is a very confusing process. Partially because the language used is often not familiar to them, partially because it implies long-term consequences on the entire project.

Results from co-design session - Documentation/Front end

Table 8: Documentation front end and backend

DOCUMENTATION FRONT END	
Results from co-design session	
General	The documentation is the step by step guide to reproduce a Careable (generic platform user, the “recipe” version).
	It shows the most updated and tested solutions developed by the team (even with the collaboration of the platform community). Its structure must be simple but detailed enough to prevent common mistakes.
	Besides the step by step guide, the overall research and even past versions of the Careable should be available for the platform users (expert level and working team, the “research” version).
Replicability of the Careable	3 status tags define the project <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Publication (public/private) ● Status (Work In Progress vs Ready) ● License (open by default)
	Estimates cost and price (if sold)
	Difficulty (0-5 level)
	Required tools
	Required skills
Safety	Validated or not by a specialist (checkbox)
	How many time has been downloaded, replicated, modified
	List members and skills (“validation” by reputation)
	If no healthcare professionals are on the team <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Alert ● Suggest to consult a specialist ● Search for a compatible specialist within the platform users
Effectiveness	Description of the goal of the Careable: what it empowers you to do
Diffusion	The template allows the team to download the documentation as an easily readable and shareable document (at least pdf. Hopefully in MD, HTML, as well)

Table 9: Documentation backend

DOCUMENTATION BACKEND	
Results from co-design session	
General	Tag for steps and info to filter “Final Recipe” from “Project Diary” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Project diary includes: ● Process done ● Research ● Intermediate prototypes ● Errors ● Etc. Careable recipe includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Header ● List of tools ● List of skills ● List of technologies ● List of material to buy ● Step by step instructions
How to document a Careable guide	List of material that needs to be collected (pictures of the step, credits, etc.) How to take pictures (brief and with basic tools) How to make videos (brief and with basic tools) Tool offline? (TBD) - based on wevolver app
Contents of the documentation	Research (not in “recipe”): not a predefined format, allows text and media Step (in the “recipe”): could be a make step or a test step, based on the objective of the operation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● box to tick if it’s a test Step (in the “recipe”): not a predefined number of steps <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Button to add another step BOM: bill of material will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Be called “what to buy” to make it more comprehensible ● Created uploading a CSV file (initially) ● Automatically created adding all the “components” in the steps. This will allow more robust customization and editing, considering that the BOM is regenerated every time a step is edited (later on) Language: not required a “scientifically correct” language

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● it's more important to be comprehensible, eventually suggesting tools like an automatic check (e.g. https://xkcd.com/simplewriter/) to underline words that could require extra explanations (i.e. [...] I have hemiplegia, a paralysis on my left side, [...]) ● Scientific credibility is provided by the healthcare professional involved
WIP vs. Finished	<p>Translations: a predefined set of languages to be used will be defined. Translation will be managed via Google translate</p> <p>Offline edit: extra versioning control tools are available in the offline desktop app for more technical users</p> <p>Documentation must accept comment and suggestions (the equivalent of “pull requests” and “issue tracker”) because they are tools to involve people and allow online collaboration</p> <p>Show a “percentage of readiness”</p>
Reusable Blocks of knowledge	<p>Possibility to aggregate and share sub-parts: some set of actions could be commonly used in Careables' creation. These parts could be selected, aggregated and integrated into another documentation. It also helps to assign credits to the authors</p>

3.3.2 Next steps: Documentation Structure

Based on above mentioned results, we outline the structure of next template:

The screenshot displays a documentation tool interface with several sections and callouts:

- Step 1 . Description:**
 - Callout 33 points to the step title.
 - Callout 27 points to the "files needed" download button.
 - Callout 28 points to the "NEEDED:" label.
 - Callout 29 points to the step description text.
 - Callout 30 points to the step description text.
 - Callout 31 points to the "DONE DIFFERENTLY?" button.
 - Callout 32 points to the "ANY ISSUES?" button.
- Step n . GROUP: Description:**
 - Callout 34 points to the step title.
 - Callout 35 points to the "documented by: Author, author, author" text.
 - Callout 36 points to a diagram showing a group of 15 steps.
- Step m . TEST: Description:**
 - Callout 37 points to the step title.
 - Callout 38 points to the "OBJECTIVE OF THE TEST:" section.
 - Callout 39 points to the "PASSED IF:" section.
 - Callout 40 points to the "HOW TO DO IT:" section.
 - Callout 41 points to the "DONE DIFFERENTLY?" button.
 - Callout 42 points to the "TEST NOT PASSED?" button.
- CREDITS:**
 - Callout 43 points to the "MAKERS: name, name, name" section.
 - Callout 44 points to the "CARE RECEIVER: name, name, name" section.
 - Callout 45 points to the "HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONAL: name, name" section.
- Download Buttons:**
 - Callout 46 points to the "download documentation in PDF" button.
 - Callout 47 points to the "download documentation in HTML" button.

In reference of the template above, the bullet point explanation is listed here:

1. *“Approved” logo*: a logo next to the title to recognize projects done in collaboration with HP that guarantee the functionality.
2. *Question Mark*: a button that triggers a pop-up with extra info on the icon/function associated with.
3. *Languages available*: we aim to have an original language version, and a set of automatically generated one, open for editing by the users.
4. *Cover image or video*: clear picture or video that represents the project. Used in the gallery too.
5. *Progress Bar*: describe approximately the state of the project, defined by the team, moving a slider or selecting the project state:
 - a. need definition -> 15%
 - b. creation of the team -> 25%
 - c. Concept -> 35%
 - d. preliminary design ->50%
 - e. preliminary prototype -> 65%
 - f. final design ->75%
 - g. tested design -> 90%
 - h. Careable: 100% - completed
6. *Private or public project*: while the project is uncompleted it can be private, and not visible from other users.
7. *Difficulty level*: defined by the team members, or automatically generated based on the number of skills listed.
8. *Time*: generated automatically by adding all the times defined in the steps. It is an approximation, but it gives an idea of the effort required.
9. *Cost*: generated automatically by the cost described in the list of materials to buy (BOM). it is an approximation but it gives an idea of the effort required.
10. *Buy*: if a team is interested in producing the Careable for others, it can be bought.
11. *Openness*: an automatically generated score based on the ticked checkboxes of the open-o-meter (or of a similar tool).
12. *License*: by default is suggested open hardware + open software license, but the team is free to choose a more restrictive one. The possible licenses will be defined later on.
13. *HP Approved*: the Careable validation relies on the HP involved in the team. If he/she confirm that the Careable is properly designed to toggle the need, then this box is checked. It is not comparable to certification, but it wants to guarantee that an HP is satisfied with its functionality.
14. *Complete research version*: it makes visible the steps not required for the

final “recipe” version. These include: failed experiments, previous versions, the original version of edited steps, etc.

15. *Download\views\replication counters*: a collection of counters is added to have statistics and give feedback to the users about their projects.
16. *List of derivatives\forks*: to simplify the definition, no versioning control language is used. The projects are described as “modified versions”. The list could be a gallery with thumbnails or a list of shortened links.
17. *Goals*: the documentation starts describing the “why” of the project. To simplify the comprehension for the user documented, it describes what to write in: “what this Careable enables you to do”.
18. *Personal story*: brief intro about the CR. it helps to understand the context of the solution and could help other CR to evaluate if the same Careable could be useful to them.
19. *Description of the need*: a focus on the limitation faced is added, the language can be simple and colloquial with medical definitions and terms if needed.
20. *Status*: it collects feedback from the status of the project. It is not related to the progress bar (point num 5.).
21. *Tools*: it is a list automatically generated by adding all the hand and power tools listed in the steps. It is not including expensive machines, digital technologies, professional machines, and everything is not easily available in tool boxes and stores.
22. *Machines*: it is a list automatically generated by adding all the expensive machines, digital technologies, professional machines listed in the steps. It is suggested to use mainly technologies easy to use and have direct or indirect access to, so a 3D printer is to be preferred (when possible) to a press.
23. *Skills*: it is a list automatically generated by adding all the skills needed and listed in the steps.
24. *Local Materials*: in the BOM (called “what to buy - materials needed”) if the components are easily found locally, no links are required. In alternative, an example can be linked.
25. *Local\online materials*: if the material can be easily found online and locally, a link must be added as a reference.
26. *Online materials*: if the material is available only\mainly online, a link must be added.
27. *Files needed for the specific step*: to facilitate flexibility in the documentation, files are linked to the sted they refer to.
28. *Estimated time for the step*: an approximate estimation of the time is required. This information is used to generate the overall time required,

described in the first part (point 8).

29. *Tools, machines, and skills per step*: each step has a list of tools, machines, and skills. It is used to create the complete lists in the first part (points 21, 22, 23).
30. *Description*: a free field is available to describe what the step is.
31. *Issues*: it refers to the “issue tracker” system, without using the same language. It is a way to keep track and raise an alert if there is a problem with the specific step.
32. *Done differently*: it refers to the possibility to submit changes or alternatives, describes a fork and asks for a pull request.
33. *“Make” step icon*: three different possible steps are available. When it refers to an action to realize the Careable it has this icon.
34. *“Group” icon*: three different possible steps are available. When it refers to a group of actions, it has this icon. It is possible to embed another documentation, meant to be more technical and focused on commonly reusable sub-tasks. *(This function is not necessary going to be implemented: it has been suggested during the codesign sessions, but not validated yet by users).*
35. *“Group” credits*: in all the groups, the credits are always visible. It is a gratification to the authors and it fulfills the open source licenses requests *(This function is not necessary going to be implemented: it has been suggested during the codesign sessions, but not validated yet by users).*
36. *Objectives*: the test steps are meant to be flexible and adjustable, just to don't overcomplicate the process. It is important to clarify why some aspects are tested. *(This function is not necessary going to be implemented: it has been suggested during the codesign sessions, but not validated yet by users).*
37. *Minimum requirements to pass*: a list of minimum requirement is described.
38. *Test description*: a description of how to perform the test is provided.
39. *Not passed*: it is important to collect feedbacks on why the product is failing the tests provided.
40. *Test done differently*: suggestions on how to perform tests with similar objectives in different ways can be provided by users.
41. *List of makers in the team.*
42. *List of the care receivers in the team.*
43. *List of the healthcare professionals in the team.*
44. *Download the documentation in pdf*: once done the documentation can be downloaded in a printable format.
45. *Download the documentation in other format*: once done the documentation can be downloaded in an easy to edit and publish format. Even if the

documentation tool is hosted on Careables.org, it is important to allow the same material to be shared on other existing platforms or on team's members' personal websites.

3.3.2 Next Steps: User Interface and Interaction

We chose to create a design with a clean and simple interface. To deal with multiple segments like files, documentation, assembly instructions, and communication tools this has been one of our main focus points. We chose this design because it puts the main emphasis on the content and removes any clutter that could confuse a user. We have simplified the interface by keeping a basic color palette and being extremely selective with features. By showing only key features to both create, and access a project we prevent confusing users.

The platform from the perspective of users documenting a project guides them from start to finish, letting them follow a series of simple guidelines. After going through these guidelines their project is presented and they are in a clean environment that gives them full freedom to add content and improve their work. The goal is to create the most organic experience as possible. To do so, we benchmarked external platforms and looked at the pros and cons of their user experience, and implemented the best practices. Therefore, we have been able to create a fast, clean, and reliable frontend interface with a powerful backend database.

From a visitors perspective there are elaborate discovery features to find the right solutions. Visitors can use "tag" browsing, which enables them to search projects based on tags which are assigned to projects by project creators. Each project is tagged with multiple tags which enables a visitor to find a project, look at its tags and discover new content. For example; a 3d printed bionic arm will be tagged "prosthetic", "3D-printing", and "arms" The visitor can now click on any of these tags and discover more solutions.

The search functionality enables a visitor to type in a direct search on the Careables platform and look for very specific solutions. The search algorithm indexes both the text that was added to the project, as well as text documents and PDF's. This increases the chance of finding a specific solution. After entering a search term, a list of solutions is shown, and the entered search terms are highlighted in bold.

Users can follow a project, tag or user with just one click. This will keep them updated when any of these update their project or if new work is shared in a

certain tag. It also adds them to their personal bookmarks list, so they can easily return to them on a later date in time.

The similar projects feature shows recommended projects to look at. These projects are based on the current solution a visitor is looking at. This improves the discoverability of new projects, and encourages further browsing and exploration of the platform.

Talks is the feature which is shown under each project. This functionality enables users to respond or ask questions under each solution. Users can post a new comment, or reply to a previous comment.

Each comment shows a user profile image and is linked to a user profile. This profile enables people to create both a Careable identity (show what projects they work on and their recent activity) as well as their external identity (Show what they do in their day to day life, link to external social media, etc).

The frontend uses React, a JavaScript library for building user interfaces. It is maintained by Facebook and a community of individual developers and companies. This enables us to quickly iterate, get feedback from the community in case there are issues, and take advantage from new features and upgrades which are developed by the developer community.

ANNEX

Annex 1: User Field Test

Annex 2: Survey templates

Annex 3: Documentation overview on Careables.org

Annex 1: User field test

User field test	
GOALS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● to observe how people search for the solutions they need ● ho have a feedback on what are the obstacles approaching the “documentation for makers”
PARTICIPANTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● C. is 47 years old. She has a 5 years old daughter, with cerebral palsy and she is the one looking after her. Her husband has a good job and she really cares about finding functional and beautiful solutions. Some friends suggested to build what she wasn't able to find, but she is not a “practical” person ● S. is a young therapist, quite shy and sensitive. She feels uncomfortable with technologies, but she knows a bit about 3D printing and other digital fabrication technologies, even if she never used them.

Test 1: SEARCHING FOR SOLUTIONS

Assigned task: look for something you need on the net

S was interested to find:

- 1- postural tool for a 17 years old boy, to have an alternative seat to the wheelchair
- 2- orthosis for the knee to be used while sleeping
- 3- something to lift a kid from the bed

OBSERVATIONS

SEARCHING

S

- . starts from the proper name of the object (e.g. “tutore”, brace) and its function (e.g. “per mantenere la posizione”, to maintain the position) and gradually adds pathology, specific features (e.g. firm vs flexible) or target (e.g. children with palsy);
- . writes “complex” sentences, adding also prepositions and not single keywords (e.g. “per bambini con pci”, for children with cerebral palsy);
- . uses words belonging to a specific register (sector: healthcare) e.g. “ausilio”, “tutore”, “tetraparesi”;
- . refines her searches results looking for the proper keyword for the object in

PLATFORM V1 INCLUDING DOCUMENTATION TOOL

scientific reports;

- . while searching she “tries” the autocomplete of Google Web search;
- . refines the searches results, clicking on interesting images/websites and using targeted terms she finds out.

CHECKING RESULTS

S

- . starts from “All” Google search results and analyses only page one;
- . opens both websites of orthopedic shops/specialists and generic sites like kijiji or trovaprezzi (similar to “pricegrabber” and “shopzilla”).

C was interested to find:

- 1- waterproof beach chair, that can be used while taking a shower as well
- 2- postural seat
- 3- small gloves with velcro to grab toys

Observations

OBSERVATIONS

SEARCHING

C

- . uses keywords with suffixes of Italian languages expressing endearment, limiting the possible range of results (e.g. “guantini”, little gloves or “sdraietta”, lovely deck chair)
- . adds aesthetic requirements in the first search (e.g. “colorata”, colorful or “di legno”, wooden)
- . doesn’t use proper keyword defining the object (e.g. statica) and she doesn’t change it during her search, even if she comes across with the correct keyword (e.g. stabilizzatore vs statica)
- . writes “complex” sentences, adding also prepositions and not single keywords (e.g. “per bambini disabili”, for children with disabilities)
- . describes the target generically (children with disabilities) and not by pathology;
- . defines object’s function with nouns vs verbs (e.g. “per giochi”, for playful activities, “uso mare”, for the seaside)
- . concentrates her search on a specific object function, even if she declares from the beginning that the object (a seat) shall be used both at the seaside and while having a shower.

CHECKING RESULTS

- . looks for “known” objects, subjects of other previous searches;
- . checks only Images Google search results;
- . scrolls many pages/images even when the results are not relevant.

THINGS EMERGED WHILE TALKING

S:

- . normally prefers Italian rather than English in her searches;
- . uses English if no significant results are turned / if she knows foreign companies designing that kind of products
- . saves interesting images as Favourites (no Pinterest or similar bookmarking tool)
- . saves interesting images with 2 objectives: to get inspiration / to think of possible adaptations of devices to patient’s needs

C:

- . uses only Italian in her searches;
- . can’t speak English;
- . saves interesting images as Favourites (no Pinterest or similar bookmarking tool);
- . saves in order to evaluate the purchase. She puts in contact with producers for info regarding price, measures and delivery time. Even if it’s not a “perfect match” she still considers to buy it to check of modify it if not too expensive;
- . is interested in aesthetic quality of products;
- . prefers buying than making.

Test 2: SEARCHING FOR SOLUTIONS

Assigned task: look for something you need on the net keeping in mind some helpful search tips given by the facilitator

OBSERVATIONS

S

- . starts looking at images results only;
- . writes “complex” sentences, adding also prepositions and not single keywords (e.g. “come sollevare un bambino disabile”, how to lift a child with disabilities);
- . knows exactly what are patient’s needs and professionals needs, can describe the main object’s requested features but she can’t imagine how the solution can be (quite common the difficulties in “designing” a solution from scratch).

C

- . doesn't apply the suggested searching method and she continues to use the same keywords and "complex" sentences;
- . influenced by Silvia, she adds pathology in her keywords.

Test 3: LOOKING AT WEVOLVER PLATFORM

Assigned task: Can you explain how the object is made, what a user needs to replicate it, how to find the information? S. and C. worked together.

Object 1: Made in shoes_ comments on Wevolver project documentation

- . the video simplifies the construction process: it could be good to have a video description of the final object and a separate one of the assembling or of the most tricky parts;
- . it is not easy to understand what the shoes are made of: they didn't know about bi-component materials;
- . no idea what a BOM is and they would like to have links where to buy and an overall price;
- . images section doesn't foresee preview;
- . there are no images of other users replicating the shoes.

Object 2: Hackaberry _ comments on Wevolver project documentation

- . better specify functions of the “object”
- . foresee the possibility to assign specific task to others -> they want to assign the construction of some parts to others
- . they are not sure where to search because there is no folder named “how to make it”
- . S would be interested in being involved in test phases with patients

Object 3: Braille smartphone keypad _ comments on Wevolver project documentation:

- . there is no video explaining the construction process
- . electronic is considered an impossible task by the two women, they're not even sure who they should ask help to (they said a vague “engineers”)

Survey

This survey is conducted by the project Made4You. In Made4You we aim to facilitate the development of customizable health care devices for people with physical limitations. With this objective we are going to create a useful platform where all health care devices can be found. We hope to benefit people with disability in their daily lives.

To build the platform we have created this survey. So your input would be really precious to us.

When answering the survey, please be aware that there are no "right" or "wrong" answers. Please mark the answer, which is closest to what you think and do not leave out any questions.

The questionnaire contains 19 questions and will take you maximum 5 minutes to answer. The survey is strictly confidential! Data will be handled completely anonymously and will not be passed on to third parties.

If you are interested to receive the anonymised results of the survey or stay in contact with us, please leave your e-mail address at the end of the survey.

* Required

Maker platforms

In the following question block we would like to learn from you about interesting maker platforms.

1. Are you familiar with these platforms? *

Check all that apply.

Github

Instructables

Wevolver

Thingiverse

MyMiniFactory

Youmagine

None of above

Other: _____

2. How did you discover this platform/these platforms? *

Check all that apply.

Specialized websites

At work

Online community/forum

Friends

I didn't know these sharing platforms

Other: _____

3. How do you use these sharing platforms? *

Please select at most 2 options

Check all that apply.

To look for ideas and projects

To draw attention to my projects

To sell the projects to other users

To spread open source projects that may be useful for others

To find collaborations

To find jobs

I don't use sharing platforms

Other: _____

4. Which platform do you use most often and like most?

Only one platform!

5. Why do you think that it is the best platform?

Please select at most 2 options

Check all that apply.

- It has a large community of makers
- My projects gain great visibility
- Documentation is easy, the form is simple to fill in
- It's a specialized platform and it is suitable for my projects
- I can apply to design competitions on the platform
- This platform is recognized by interesting companies
- Other: _____

6. When you use sharing platforms, which features are important to you? *

1= not at all important - 5 = very important

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5
Feature to reuse and modify other's projects	<input type="radio"/>				
Tool for parametric projects	<input type="radio"/>				
Crowdfunding option	<input type="radio"/>				
Feature to save interesting projects	<input type="radio"/>				
Preview of similar projects	<input type="radio"/>				
Statistics/likes/ views	<input type="radio"/>				
Forum/chat/comments	<input type="radio"/>				
Guided documentation with tutorials	<input type="radio"/>				

Finding Careables

Careables are devices conceived for people with physical limitations that can be created by anyone following the given instructions. They are made by means of digital fabrication technologies.

In the following question block we would like to learn how to best tag Careables to make them search and findable in the community of makers.

This is a careable:

7. How would you tag a careable? How should a Careable be tagged to be trackable? Please rank the following tags for the Careable above in order of importance (from 1= least important to 8=most important). *

1= least important - 8 = most important

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
customizable	<input type="radio"/>							
3dprinter	<input type="radio"/>							
writing	<input type="radio"/>							
children	<input type="radio"/>							
disability	<input type="radio"/>							
plastic	<input type="radio"/>							
cerebral palsy	<input type="radio"/>							
accessibility	<input type="radio"/>							

8. Have you ever developed a careable? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes *Skip to question 9.*

No *Skip to question 13.*

Creating Careables

In this section we would be interested to learn from your experiences with creating a Careable

9. Why did you make the first careable? *

Mark only one oval.

- It was for me
- It was for an acquaintance, family member and/or friend
- It was developed during a specific event eg. Hackathon
- It was a contracted service
- I was inspired by others
- I wanted to improve an interesting project from another maker
- Other: _____

10. Which difficulties have you encountered while creating careables? Please use the following rating. *

1= Never, 2=Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Very Often, 5= Always

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5
To solve technological problems	<input type="radio"/>				
To find materials	<input type="radio"/>				
To test the prototype	<input type="radio"/>				
To use software/technologies I didn't know before	<input type="radio"/>				
To find tools/machines (eg. 3d printer) to create parts of my careables	<input type="radio"/>				
To talk with experts	<input type="radio"/>				
To communicate careables	<input type="radio"/>				

11. Where have you shown your careables? *

Check all that apply.

- Github
- Instructables
- Wevolver
- Thingiverse
- Myminifactory
- Youmagine
- I built a careable website
- I didn't share my careables
- Other: _____

12. If you didn't share your careable, why?

Please select at most 2 options.

Check all that apply.

- I am not interested
- It is a product conceived for the market and not an open source project
- Writing down documentation is too difficult
- I want to copyright my idea
- It is just a prototype
- It is not medically certified
- Other: _____

Co-designing Careables

Co-designing means collaborating in heterogeneous teams and putting together diverse competences, needs, experiences and skills to come up with a new solution. One of the participants is the person with needs.

In the following question block we would like to learn from your experiences or ideas about co-designing Careables.

13. In a heterogeneous working group composed by doctors, patients, caregivers and you, what might be challenges for you? *

Please select at most 2 options

Check all that apply.

- I speak a too technical language
- I don't have experience in the social sector
- I can't understand problems of people with disabilities
- I can't understand medical terminology
- I am interested in aesthetics rather than usefulness
- Other: _____

14. A website conceived for co-designing Careables should allow me to: *

Check all that apply.

- search makers/experts/people to talk to
- create a team for my project idea
- find people interested in these issues that live close to me
- offer my help for other's projects
- share project ideas and designs
- discuss, collaborate and advance first ideas and prototypes
- find and reuse others' designs, prototypes, methodologies of co-designing
- Other: _____

About you

15. Age *

16. Where do you live? *

Mark only one oval.

- Italy
- Germany
- Austria
- Belgium
- Great Britain
- The Netherlands
- Other: _____

17. Sex *

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

18. Job *

19. Have you ever had pathologies/physical injuries - including also temporary limitation - requiring the use of devices that you might even have hacked or created yourself?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

Thanks a lot for your time and answers!

20. If you are interested to receive a summary of anonymised results to this survey or want to keep in touch with us, please leave your e-mail address.

Survey

This survey is conducted by the project Made4You. In Made4You we aim to facilitate the development of customizable health care devices for people with physical limitations. With this objective we are going to create a useful platform where all health care devices can be found. We hope to benefit people with disability in their daily lives.

To build the platform we have created this survey. So your input would be really precious to us.

When answering the survey, please be aware that there are no "right" or "wrong" answers. Please mark the answer, which is closest to what you think and do not leave out any questions.

The questionnaire contains 18 questions and will take you maximum 5 minutes to answer. The survey is strictly confidential! Data will be handled completely anonymously and will not be passed on to third parties.

If you are interested to receive the anonymised results of the survey or stay in contact with us, please leave your e-mail address at the end of the survey.

* Required

Health care devices

Health care devices are tools, appliances, objects, software and apps that support the autonomy of people in daily activities like sitting, moving or eating.

In this section we would like to learn what is important for you when searching for and suggesting health care devices to your clients.

1. In your opinion which are important features for a high quality health care device? *

1= not at all important - 5 = very important

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5
Appearance	<input type="radio"/>				
Ergonomics	<input type="radio"/>				
Functionality	<input type="radio"/>				
Certification	<input type="radio"/>				
Brand/manufacturer	<input type="radio"/>				
Price	<input type="radio"/>				
Materials	<input type="radio"/>				
Popularity	<input type="radio"/>				
Resistance	<input type="radio"/>				
Lightness	<input type="radio"/>				
Comfort	<input type="radio"/>				
Customization and adaptability	<input type="radio"/>				

2. How do you search for health care devices? *

Check all that apply.

- Catalogues of healthcare companies
- Pharmaceutical representatives
- Healthcare magazines
- E-commerce website (eg. Amazon, Ebay)
- Healthcare fairs
- Free search through online search engines
- Ortophedic companies
- Pubmed
- Other: _____

3. Which features do you value in a website presenting health care devices? *

1= not at all important - 5 = very important

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5
The website is certified by a medical association	<input type="radio"/>				
The language is clear and simple	<input type="radio"/>				
Contents are in my native language	<input type="radio"/>				
The website uses images	<input type="radio"/>				
There are explanatory videos	<input type="radio"/>				
The website includes a blog with stories from patients	<input type="radio"/>				
The website has positive feedback from patients	<input type="radio"/>				
The website has positive feedback from therapists/doctors	<input type="radio"/>				
There are scientific sheets/researches	<input type="radio"/>				

4. A patient feels uncomfortable with a prescribed health care device. If he or she proposed a device found online, how would you behave? *

Mark only one oval.

- I would evaluate technical features to understand if it suitable for person's conditions
- I would talk with my colleagues
- If the source is not official, I will not prescribe the proposed device
- I would like to better understand who are the producers/manufacturers
- I would reject the proposal a priori
- Other: _____

Careables

Careables are devices conceived for people with physical limitations that can be created by anyone following the given instructions.

In the following question block we would like to learn from your experiences about suggesting and searching for Careables.

But before we start, we want to show you some examples of Careables.

Self-made prosthesis

Posture support seat for children

Gripping aids

5. Have you ever suggested a Careable to one of your patients? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

6. If yes, which difficulties did you encounter?

Check all that apply.

None

Cost of technologies/project development was high

Waiting times were too long

The patient didn't agree with it

It was hard to find collaborators for the project development

Other: _____

7. Which keywords would you use to search the following object online? *

A careable

8. How would you tag a careable? How should a Careable be tagged to be trackable? Please rank the following tags for the Careable above in order of importance (from 1= least important to 8=most important). *

1= least important - 8 = most important

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
customizable	<input type="radio"/>							
3dprinter	<input type="radio"/>							
writing	<input type="radio"/>							
children	<input type="radio"/>							
disability	<input type="radio"/>							
plastic	<input type="radio"/>							
cerebral palsy	<input type="radio"/>							
accessibility	<input type="radio"/>							

Digital fabrication technologies

Digital fabrication makes use of new technologies to allow anyone to design and develop personalised products.

In the following question block we would like to learn about your experience with these tools.

9. Which digital fabrication technologies do you know? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Have never heard about it	Have heard about it	Have some experience	Am expert on using it
3d printer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Arduino	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Laser cutter	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Milling machine	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Software programming	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
App programming	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Careables platforms

In the following question block we would like to collect from you input in order to build a useful platform

10. If you think about a platform where you can look for Careables. Which platform would you use most likely? Which structure do you prefer? *

Mark only one oval.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

1

2

3

4

11. Which information would you need about a specific Careable. In the following section we show you several project pages, always presenting a Careable. Which one would you prefer? *

Mark only one oval.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

1

2

3

4

Co-designing Careables

Co-designing means collaborating in a heterogeneous team, putting together diverse competences, needs, experiences, skills to come up with a new solution.

In the following question block we would like to learn your experiences and ideas about co-designing Careables.

12. In a heterogeneous working group composed by designers, patients, caregivers and you, what what might be challenges for you? *

Please select at least 2 options

Check all that apply.

- I speak a too technical language
- I have to share responsibility in the decision taking
- I have to use not conventional methodologies/processes
- I have to approach technologies I don't know
- I reveal too much private information from my patients
- Other: _____

13. A website conceived for co-designing should allow me to: *

Check all that apply.

- search colleagues/experts/people to talk to
- create a team for my project idea
- find people interested in these issues that live close to me
- offer my help for other's projects
- find and reuse others' designs, prototypes, methodologies of co-designing
- discuss, collaborate and advance first ideas and prototypes
- share project ideas and designs
- Other: _____

About you

14. Age *

15. Where do you live? *

Mark only one oval.

- Italy
- Germany
- Austria
- Belgium
- Great Britain
- The Netherlands
- Other: _____

16. Sex *

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

17. Job *

18. Have you ever had pathologies/physical injuries - including also temporary limitation - requiring the use of devices?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Thanks a lot for your time and answers!

19. If you are interested to receive a summary of anonymised results to this survey or want to keep in touch with us, please leave your e-mail address.

Powered by

 Google Forms

Survey

This survey is conducted by the project Made4You. In Made4You we aim to facilitate the development of customizable health care devices for people with physical limitations. With this objective we are going to create a useful platform where all health care devices can be found. We hope to benefit people with disability in their daily lives.

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If you are interested to receive the anonymised results of the survey or stay in contact with us, please leave your e-mail address at the end of the survey.

* Required

Searching for health care devices

Health care devices are tools, objects, appliances, software and apps that support the autonomy of people in their daily activities like sitting, moving or eating.

In this question block we would like to learn from your experiences with searching for and using health care devices.

1. Have you ever thought that an health care device doesn't fit your needs or the needs of an acquaintance of yours? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

2. If yes, why?

Please select at most 2 options

Check all that apply.

- It is not beautiful
- It is not useful
- It is not ergonomic
- It is too big/too small
- Use causes pain/side effects/complaints
- Other: _____

3. Who did you talk to about this problem?

Check all that apply.

- My doctor
- My relatives
- My friends/acquaintance of mine
- Specialized online forum
- Only with strangers
- Nobody
- Other: _____

4. Have you ever looked for alternative solutions besides prescribed devices? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

5. Which website do you visit to look for health care devices? *

Check all that apply.

- Websites of local/national health authorities
- Websites of patient organisations dealing with specific pathologies
- Wikipedia
- Online forum dedicated to health and wellbeing issues
- Healthcare magazines and websites
- E-commerce websites (eg. Amazon)
- Pinterest or similar websites
- I usually don't look for medical devices
- Other: _____

6. If you don't look for health care devices, what is the reason?

Please select at most 2 options

Check all that apply.

- I always speak with my therapist/doctor
- I have never taken into account this possibility
- I don't think I can find solutions online
- Online shopping can be stressful: often you do not get the item you expected
- I generally don't purchase products connected to my health online
- I don't need it, the devices I am using are suitable for me
- Other: _____

7. What do you value while searching health information online? *

1= not at all important - 5 = very important

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5
simple/clear language	<input type="radio"/>				
contents in my language	<input type="radio"/>				
use of images	<input type="radio"/>				
use of explanatory videos	<input type="radio"/>				
blog with stories of other users like me	<input type="radio"/>				
positive feedback from other users like me	<input type="radio"/>				
scientific sheets	<input type="radio"/>				
practical suggestions of doctors/experts	<input type="radio"/>				

Careables

Careables are devices conceived for people with physical limitations that can be created by anyone following the given instructions.

In the following question block we would like to learn from your experiences about suggesting and searching for Careables.

But before we start, we want to show you some examples of Careables.

Self-made prosthesis

Posture support seat for children

Gripping aids

8. Which aspects are/or would be important determinants for you to use a Careable? *

1= not at all important - 5 = very important

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5
security	<input type="radio"/>				
certification	<input type="radio"/>				
doctor's opinion	<input type="radio"/>				
possibility to customize it	<input type="radio"/>				
typology of materials	<input type="radio"/>				
possibility to ask more information to the authors	<input type="radio"/>				
positive feedback from people with similar needs/conditions	<input type="radio"/>				

9. Have you ever modified a device/aid/tool in order to adapt it to your personal needs? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

10. Which keywords would you use to search the following Careable online? *

Careables platforms

In the following question block we would like to collect your input in order to build a useful platform for Careables.

11. If you think about a platform where you can look for Careables. Which platform would you use most likely? Which structure do you prefer? *

Mark only one oval.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

1

2

3

4

12. Which information would you need about a specific Careable? In the following section we show you several project pages, always presenting a Careable. Which one would you prefer? *

Mark only one oval.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

1

2

3

4

Co-designing Careables

Co-designing means working together in a heterogeneous team, putting together diverse competences, needs, experiences and skills to come up with a new solution.

In the following question block we would like to learn your experiences or ideas about co-designing Careables.

13. **In a heterogeneous working group composed by designers, doctors and you, what might be challenges for you? ***

Please select at most 2 options

Check all that apply.

- I am not able to understand the co-designing process
- I can't understand what people talk about
- I feel used
- I don't think my contribution is relevant
- I can't see benefits in participating in the process
- I fear that I have to provide intimate information
- Other: _____

14. **While interacting with experts (e.g. health professionals or makers), what is the most difficult thing? ***

Mark only one oval.

- To talk about personal aspects
- To explain my medical problems
- To understand technical language
- To contribute to the discussion
- Other: _____

15. **A website conceived for co-designing should allow me to: ***

Check all that apply.

- search people with problems/needs/conditions that are similar to mine
- create a team for my project idea
- find people interested in these issues that live close to me
- offer my help for other's projects
- find and reuse others' designs, prototypes, methodologies of co-designing
- discuss, collaborate and advance first ideas and prototypes
- share project ideas and designs
- Other: _____

About you

16. **Age ***

17. Where do you live? *

Mark only one oval.

- Italy
- Germany
- Austria
- Belgium
- Great Britain
- The Netherlands
- Other: _____

18. Sex *

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

19. Job *

20. Have you ever had pathologies/physical injuries - including also temporary limitations - requiring the use of devices?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

21. Have you ever had pathologies/physical injuries - including also temporary limitations - requiring the use of devices/solutions you modified/made yourself?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

Thanks a lot for your time and answers!

22. If you are interested to receive a summary of anonymised results to this survey or want to keep in touch with us, please leave your e-mail address.

Done

Project Creation Wizard

CREATE PROJECT

BASICS

Thumbnail

Title

Description: Pitch your project in 90 characters or less.

Privacy

- Public**
Anyone can see this project. You choose who can modify it.
- Private**
You choose who can see and modify this project.

PROJECT OVERVIEW

Youtube URL: Do you have a project video?

No video? [Start your overview with a banner image instead](#)

Summary: How would you explain your project?

Add images to Project Summary
JPEG, PNG or GIF • 2MB file limit

Goal: What does this project aim to accomplish?

Add images to Project Goal
JPEG, PNG or GIF • 2MB file limit

Specifications: Did the project need to meet any requirements?

Add images to Technical Specifications
JPEG, PNG or GIF • 2MB file limit

Roadmap (optional): What future work is planned?

Add images to Project Roadmap
JPEG, PNG or GIF • 2MB file limit

Team: Who worked on this project?

Add images to Team
JPEG, PNG or GIF • 2MB file limit

CREATE

CAREABLES WIZARD

CAREABLES PROJECT

The screenshot shows a web browser window with a grey header and a white main content area. The browser's address bar is empty. The page title is "Hackberry 3D-printable Open-source Bionic Arm /". The author is listed as "Cameron Norris/". There are "CLONE" and "FOLLOW" buttons. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column contains a file list with "documentation.md" (3 kb). The right column features a video player with a play button and a "YouTube" logo. Below the video is a detailed description of the project, including its creator, licensing, and a project goal.

DISCOVER WEVOLVER STAFF

Cameron Norris/
Hackberry 3D-printable Open-source Bionic Arm / CLONE FOLLOW

Images
documentation.md 3 kb

Hackberry 3D-printable Open-source Bionic Arm

- Created by *exiii Inc. & Mission ARM Japan*
- Licensed under *CC BY-SA 4.0*

The HACKberry is a 3D printable electric prosthetic arm created by exiii Inc a Japanese robotics company based in Tokyo and specialised in bionic arms.

The hand works by detecting when nerve and muscle tissue is stimulated by signals from the brain and sends that data to an onboard micro controller to translate into hand and arm movements. The system enables users of the prosthesis to open and close the hand and even control individual fingers. The hand uses an underactuated mechanism to control precise movements and obtain self-adaptability when grasping different objects with its 3DOF fingers.

After the initial designs were released as open source files the project created a stir on social media site Reddit. This resulted in further collaborative development of the Hackberry by a community, including highly skilled engineers, designers, medics and manufacturing companies.

Project Goal:

We have released the design data of HACKberry, our latest 3D-printed bionic hand, as open source for the purpose of speeding up development through participation of collaborators from all over the world. In addition, we hope that collaborators will deliver this artificial arm to those we cannot reach

Assembly Guides

ASSEMBLY GUIDES

- Images
- Video's (copy/paste)

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the Festo AquaJellies project page. The browser's address bar shows navigation icons and a search bar. The page header includes 'Festo AquaJellies' and navigation links: 'DISCOVER', 'START PROJECT', and 'SEARCH'. On the right side, there are buttons for 'PROJECT HISTORY' and 'FILE HISTORY'. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column contains a list of files: 'Overview' (4 kB) and 'Assembly Guide' (1 kB), with buttons for 'ADD GUIDE' and 'ADD FILES'. The right column is titled 'Assembly Guide' and features three numbered steps (1, 2, 3) with corresponding images. Below the steps are buttons for 'REARRANGE STEPS' and 'ADD STEP'. The first step, 'Step 1 Step 1', includes an image of a red and white modular robot and a list of resources: 'Bill of materials', 'List of 3D printed parts', 'Schematics', and 'STL files for printing'. The second step, 'Step 2 Step 2', includes a video player showing a red and white modular robot on a green surface and a list of parts: '2 x Part 004-1' and '1 x Part 011-1'. The third step, 'Step 3 Step 3', includes an image of a grey servomotor and a list of instructions: 'Take apart the back cover of the servomotor (4 screws)'.

ASSEMBLY GUIDES

- Images
- Video's (copy/paste)

Frontend upgraded to React

JavaScript library for
building user interfaces
maintained by Facebook

2 / 4 times faster

EDITOR

- More user friendly
- More options

Yale University
Yale OpenHand Project Model T
3d Printing | Robotic Hands | Grippers | Under Actuation | Research Platforms

PROJECT HISTORY

Overview 4 kB
Images

ADD FILES

SAVE

Overview

OpenHand Model T42 Performance (Autonomous Gras...
Later bekijken Delen

A 3D-printed robotic hand with underactuated fingers and compliant flexure joints.

The model T is an open-source, low-cost, robotic hand that can be created through rapid-prototyping techniques and off-the-shelf components.

pulley tree differential. During grasp acquisition, each finger will continue to move until the links make contact with the object, reducing the need for sensors or feedback control.

To make sure the hand is compatible with 3D printing technologies, the finger designs are converted to structures that have a minimal number of small features and parts.

Specifications

Description	Metric
Fingers	4
Bas height (mm)	75-90
Base Width (mm)	100
Weight (g)	400
Grip Force (N)	10
Actuators	1
Material	ABS
Fabrication	shape deposition manufacturing (SDM)
Costs	\$500

TAG FOLLOWING

- Returning visitors

Tagged with
Rehabilitation FOLLOW 68

Huggable Robot 97
The Huggable is a robotic companion capable of active relational interactions.
Haptic Feedback Human-Robot Interaction
Rehabilitation
06 Oct 2018 - MIT

Simple-structured Pneumatic Robot Arm 44
Flexible robot arm applied into a rehabilitation device for the human wrist.
Mckibben Muscles Pneumatic Muscles
Rehabilitation
11 Sep 2018 - Okayama University of Science

Mindwalker 157
An exoskeleton that is equipped with powerful actuators to support knee extension.
Exoskeletons Healthcare Rehabilitation
06 Sep 2018 - Delft University of Technology

Rehabilitation Robot 142
A sitting/lying multi-joint LLR-Ro that is designed to help people with injuries.
Healthcare Rehabilitation
05 Sep 2018 - Yanshan University

Knee Exoskeleton 190
An energetically-autonomous powered knee exoskeleton to facilitate running.
Exoskeletons Rehabilitation
04 Sep 2018 - Yale

Harmony - Upper-body Rehabilitation E... 180
An exoskeleton consisting of an anatomical shoulder mechanism.
Exoskeletons Rehabilitation
30 Aug 2018 - University of Texas

TAGGING

- Returning visitors

MIT
Huggable Robot
Haptic Feedback Rehabilitation Human-Robot Interaction

DISCOVER START PROJECT SEARCH LOG IN

FOLLOW 97

Overview 7 kB
Images

Overview

Huggable Robot Befriends Girl in Hospital
Later bekijken Delen

A robotic companion capable of active relational and affective touch-based interactions with a person.

The robot is being designed to function both as a fully autonomous robot as well as a semi-autonomous robot avatar. In the semi-autonomous case, the Huggable robot is remotely controlled by a human operator.

In the head of the robot is a variety of microphones, two cameras in the eyes, and a speaker in the mouth. In the body, the robot features an inertial measurement unit based upon passive potentiometers in the hips and ankles for joint angle position detection, an embedded PC with wireless networking.

The robot features a high number of somatic sensors (electric field, temperature, and force) over the entire surface of the robot, underneath a soft silicone skin and fur fabric covering. The Huggable consists of a series of body regions – the arms, the legs, the head, and body. The body contains an embedded PC, somatic processing sensory circuit boards, batteries, and motor driver circuit boards.

The neck and shoulder mechanisms allow for active touch behaviors such as orienting towards touch, nuzzling, and hugging. The eyebrow and ear mechanisms are used for expression of internal state.

Overview 7 kB
Images

TAGGING

- Better navigating/exploring experience

The screenshot shows a web browser window with six project cards arranged in a 2x3 grid. Each card features an image of a robot, a title, a brief description, a list of tags, and a date. The projects are: AquaJellies (underwater jellyfish robot), BionicOpter (dragonfly-inspired flying robot), PowerGripper (bird-beak inspired gripper), Bionic Handling Assistant (elephant-trunk inspired gripper), LearningGripper (pneumatic four-finger gripper), and Atlas Robot (bipedal humanoid robot).

Project Name	Description	Tags	Date	Count
AquaJellies	An artificial autonomous jellyfish with an electric drive.	Aquatic Exploration, Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs)	12 Oct 2018 - Festo	512
BionicOpter	A flying robot with the characteristics of a dragonfly.	Biomimetics, Micro Air Vehicles (MAVs)	12 Oct 2018 - Festo	578
PowerGripper	A gripper based on the kinematics of the bird's beak.	Biomimetics, Grippers, Pneumatic Actuators	12 Oct 2018 - Festo	356
Bionic Handling Assistant	A flexible gripper arm which is modelled on an elephant's trunk.	Biomimetics, Grippers, Pneumatic Actuators		344
LearningGripper	A pneumatic four-finger gripper with three degrees of freedom per finger.	Grippers, Robotic Hands		299
Atlas Robot	A bipedal humanoid robot that has been designed for various search and rescue tasks.	Bipeds, Humanoids		456

RELATED PROJECTS

- Discoverability

CATEGORIES

- Based on collection of tags.

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying a category page for 'Robotic Arms'. The browser's address bar is empty, and the page header includes navigation links for 'DISCOVER', 'START PROJECT', and 'SEARCH', along with a 'LOG IN' button. The main content area features a 'Category' section with the title 'Robotic Arms' and a 'Tags' section containing buttons for 'Robotic Arms', 'Robotic Hands', 'Grippers', 'Human-Robot Interaction', and 'Collaborative Robots'. Below this, six project cards are displayed in a grid. Each card includes a thumbnail image, a title, a brief description, a list of tags, and the date of publication. The projects are: 'AirArm' (a two-segmented arm with an external skeleton), 'PowerGripper' (a gripper based on bird kinematics), 'Bionic Handling Assistant' (a flexible gripper arm modeled on an elephant's trunk), 'LearningGripper' (a pneumatic four-finger gripper), 'Anthropomorphic Robot Hand' (a hand with a twisted string actuation mechanism), and '6 DOF Industrial Robot Arm' (an industrial arm with a hybrid kinematic design).

Category
Robotic Arms

Tags
Robotic Arms Robotic Hands Grippers Human-Robot Interaction Collaborative Robots

AirArm 213
A two-segmented arm with an external skeleton.
Biomimetics Robotic Arms
13 Oct 2018 - Festo

PowerGripper 356
A gripper based on the kinematics of the bird's beak.
Biomimetics Grippers Pneumatic Actuators
12 Oct 2018 - Festo

Bionic Handling Assistant 344
A flexible gripper arm which is modelled on an elephant's trunk.
Biomimetics Grippers Pneumatic Actuators
12 Oct 2018 - Festo

LearningGripper 299
A pneumatic four-finger gripper with three degrees of freedom per finger.

Anthropomorphic Robot Hand 357
An anthropomorphic robot hand with an active dual-mode twisted string actuation mechanism.

6 DOF Industrial Robot Arm 102
An industrial robot arm with a hybrid kinematic design.

NEXT

- **Test Create Template**
- **Test Assembly Guides**
- **Discuss “talk” functionality**